

A Different Approach to Suicide Psychology Associate Professor Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER

St. Clements University, Deputy Dean - Faculty Member

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Abstract

It is understood that suicide is a major health problem and the leading cause of death worldwide. Because, this subject, which needs much more work, needs to be explained, although it is essential to be developed in the literature. Recent reports report that approximately one million people die by suicide each year, representing the annual global age-standardized suicide rate of 11.4 (15.0 for men

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and 8.0 for women) per 100,000 population.^[1] Considering a time perspective from 2000 to 2016, there has been a 30% increase in suicide rates by age.^[2] These ratios are just the tip of an iceberg. There are many more who try suicide every year. A cautious estimate shows that more than 20 million people engage in suicidal behavior each year. In addition, considering the WHO's announcement that suicide rates will exceed the one million mark in the next 15 years, it is predicted that suicide rates will increase in the future.^[3] Behind every suicide and attempt, there is a long-term struggle of these individuals, their experiences of trauma and distress among their relatives and friends. However, preventing suicide is a global priority. As clinicians and researchers, we must make every effort to find, intervene, and after preventing suicidal behavior. Above all, our mission is to advance our knowledge by understanding the mechanisms, factors, and facilitators of suicide from interdisciplinary perspectives.

Keywords: *suicide, suicide psychology, reasons for suicide, suicide in psychology, solutions to suicide*

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Overview

Suicide is an overly complex and multifaceted phenomenon with many contributing and easing variables. Suicide can be decided by the interaction of numerous factors such as neurobiology, personal or family history, stressful events, and sociocultural environment. Considered to be one of the most violent human behaviors, finding the underlying psychological processes that may lead to suicidal ideation and behavior will be a separate focus.

Over the last century, we have recognized the contribution of psychological factors (both individual and social) to suicide and suicide risk. A number of models have been proposed, most emphasizing the interaction between predisposing and accelerating factors.^{[4], [5]}

The most important factor leading to suicide is unbearable mental pain.^[6] Many studies have emphasized the importance of psychic pain as the primary facilitator of suicidal ideation and behavior. Suicide can be seen as a behavior motivated by an overwhelming desire to escape psychological pain. Other psychological factors such as personality traits, emotional traits, and disorganization also seem to play a role, with the increasing importance of the lack of decision-making among suicidal individuals.

Interpersonal factors also play a key role in suicides. Emile Durkheim's seminal work laid the foundations for our understanding that suicide is also a social behavior with some cultural characteristics. Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide highlights two main interpersonal structures—perceived burden and denied belonging—as critical characteristics that can lead to suicidal ideation and eventual suicide.

Approximately 45% of individuals who died because of suicide consult a

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physician within one month of death, without reporting their suicidal thoughts and wishes. This finding highlights the fact that communication difficulties are the

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focus of our understanding of suicidal behavior. In the Israel MSSA (Medically Serious Suicide Attempts) project, Levi-Belz and colleagues have shown that poor character, along with several relevant factors, can facilitate suicidal behavior more lethal.^[2]

Psychological Factors

In the last century, the contribution of psychological factors (both individual and social) to suicide and suicide risk has been recognized. A number of models have been proposed, most emphasizing the interaction between predisposing and accelerating factors.

The most crucial factor leading to suicide is unbearable mental pain. Many studies have emphasized the importance of psychic pain as the primary facilitator of suicidal ideation and behavior. Suicide can be seen as a behavior motivated by the desire to escape unbearable psychological pain. Other psychological factors such as personality traits, emotional traits, and disorganization also seem to play a role,

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with the increasing importance of the lack of decision-making among suicidal individuals.

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Interpersonal factors also play a key role in suicides. The groundbreaking work of Emile Durkheim laid the foundations for our understanding that suicide is also a social behavior with some cultural characteristics. Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide highlights two main interpersonal constructs—perceived burden and denied belonging—as critical characteristics that can lead to suicidal ideation and eventual suicide.

Approximately 45% of individuals who died because of suicide consult a physician without reporting their suicidal wishes and thoughts in the month before their death. This finding highlights the fact that communication difficulties are the focus of our understanding of suicidal behavior. In the Israel MSSA (Medically Serious Suicide Attempts) project, Levi-Belz and colleagues proved that weak self-disclosure could ease more lethal suicidal behavior, with several factors involved.

These work examples are representative of numerous efforts to deepen our understanding of the psychology of the phenomenon of suicide. To continue this mode of action and thought, a special issue of *Frontiers in Psychiatry* is devoted to an effort to explore various approaches to the psychology of suicidal behavior. The aim of this study was to explore the psychological understanding of the phenomenon of suicide as well as non-suicidal self-harm (suicide attempts). This is to shed light on in-depth knowledge and empirical data on models, theories, and variables of a certain size that can help us increase the knowledge at hand.

In this sense, five encouraging reviews are presented. Gvion and Levi-Belz examined certain risk factors for serious suicide attempts (SSA). [8] Szücs et al. reiterated the importance of focusing on personality and suicidal behavior in old age in their systematic reviews. As a result of the examination of many scientific articles, he found determinations about suicide in the milder, sub-threshold and initial stages of maladaptive personality. It was also emphasized that suicide occurs in more heterogeneous forms later in life. Events occurring in advanced ages can explain the relationship between suicide and high conscientiousness in old age. Obsessive-compulsive and avoidant personality traits are especially associated

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with elderly suicide.

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Cipriano et al conducted a recent systematic review of suicide attempts focusing on epidemiological, etiological, and diagnostic criteria. Suicide attempts were found to be most common among adolescents and young adults. Borderline personality disorder and eating disorders have been reported as comorbid antecedents of suicide attempts. The prevalence rates are 7.5-46.5% for adolescents, 38.9% for university students, and 4-23% for adults. In a review article, Geraldo da Silva et al. group the main cognitive difficulties among individuals who try suicide. These include attentional bias, impulsivity, problem-solving, and decision-making deficits.[9] Finally, in the review by Conti et al, the authors systematically review the associations between eating disorders and suicidal ideation and suicide attempts.[10]

Many reviewed articles focus on finding risk factors in childhood. Schmidt et al. used structural equation modeling to test theory-based models of clinical high-risk (CHR) psychosis. CHR patients were particularly suicidal if the challenge/trauma was followed by depression. In addition, distress/trauma led to suicide through an increased risk of psychosis, as proved by cognitive symptoms.

Bar-Zomer and Brunstein-Klomek examined the relationships between problems among students, sibling bullying, excessive attachment to parents, depression, and suicidal ideation. Miscommunication between siblings has been associated with bullying, school behavior, depression, and suicidal ideation.[11th]

Falgares et al. evaluated the role of self-criticism and addiction as potential mediators of the link between different forms of childhood maltreatment and suicide among college students. Negligence and psychological abuse were significantly associated with suicide risk, and this relationship was partially mediated by the maladaptive personality dimension of self-criticism.

Risk factors

Few studies have examined risk factors for suicidal behavior in certain populations. Stein et al. In their longitudinal study of former POWs in Israel, they saw an ordered pattern. They found that the loneliness of their symptoms made it easier to experience, and these were effective for implying suicidal ideation even years after captivity. They concluded that both symptoms and loneliness were crucial factors in the long-term suicidal ideation and risk of former POWs. Mérida-López et al. examined the role of emotional intelligence (EI) as a protective factor of suicidal ideation and behavior among students and the public. They found that emotional intelligence as a mediator was associated with psychological distress and suicide risk. They concluded that self-revealing emotional intelligence may act as a protective factor against suicidal ideation and behavior and that the underlying process is through the reduction of distress among those with high emotional intelligence.

Balazs et al. examined quality of life (QoL) as a factor that may serve as a link between psychopathology and suicide risk among a clinical adolescent population. QoL significantly mediates the associations between emotional difficulties and peer problems, as both are associated with lower QoL, which in turn appears to be associated with a higher risk of suicide. Hofstra et al. He found similar information in his study of focusing on temporal suicidal tendencies among the Dutch population. They saw 33,224 suicides that occurred from 1995 to 2015. The results showed that the incidence of suicide peaks in the spring and around Christmas, emphasizing the importance of health care accessibility during these high-risk moments.

Many studies on this topic have affected other important risk factors. According to Tavakoli et al. studied the relationship between attentional control and suicidal behavior in a cohort of inpatient adolescents who show acute suicidal behavior compared to healthy controls. A passively presented auditory best paradigm was used. This "The degree to which auditory stimuli are processed was measured by

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recording event-related potentials (ERPs) thought to reflect processes associated with attention.[12] Thompson and Chen Ong investigated the relationship of

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suicidal behavior with neurological and behavioral markers by measuring attentional bias and inhibition in two Stroop tasks.

High-Risk Participants

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High-risk participants showed slower reaction times in the Stroop analysis (as in the word "suicide") and lower accuracy in their maladaptive trial, but faster

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response times (with decreased activity in the left anterior areas) in the emotional Stroop task. The results confirmed that those who tried suicide had deficits in attention control, which may be associated with certain conditions of frontal asymmetry. In another important study, Hadlaczky et al. examined the relationship between loss avoidance and suicidal behavior among adolescents recruited in 30 schools in seven European countries. Loss aversion predicted suicide attempt in both cross-sectional and 4-month prospective analyzes after controlling for depression, anxiety, stress, and gender. Interestingly, loss aversion did not predict suicidal ideation in this group.

Several innovative articles examine the core issue of therapeutic interventions for suicidal patients, with a particular focus on reducing suicide rates. First, Iyengar et al. conducted a systematic review of randomized controlled trials that reported that therapeutic interventions were effective in reducing self-harm, including suicide attempts. In addition, reductions in suicidal ideation and depressive symptoms were reported following therapeutic interventions. While most studies were unable to decide the efficacy of therapeutic interventions for both primary and secondary outcomes, individual self-directed and socially driven processes seemed to offer the greatest hope in reducing suicide attempts.

Suicidal Thoughts and Behaviors

Another contribution to prevention is that of Pickering et al. and 3,730 people 9-12, who worked on an intervention program where students trained as peer leaders for a year. It is about educating more peer leaders, increasing school-wide exposure for all modalities, as well as assessing a grader's friendships at school and adults, as well as suicidal thoughts and behaviors in general. Exposure was higher for students who were closer to peer leaders in the peer network and for students who were referred to as more trusted adults. Relatedly, Barzilay et al. approved the Therapist Response Questionnaire-Suicide Form (TRQ-SF) in a general outpatient setting in a cohort of adult psychiatric patients and therapists.[13] In a seminal study, Brodsky et al. discussed and intervened in the suicide prevention model as a guide for the implementation of the Zero Suicide model, a framework for coordinating a multi-level approach to implement evidence-based practice in clinical settings. The article describes the ten essential steps for clinical management and shows how to apply them through a clinical sketch. Finally, Sakashita and Oyama present the integration of suicidal-related psycho-behavioral components, existing guidelines for finding critical intervention points, and a preventive strategies framework into a theoretical model for elder suicidality.

These two articles examine different issues related to more suicide. Moreno-Küstner et al. When analyzing the characteristics of 181,824 calls for suicidal behavior to the Malaga Pre-Hospital Emergency Department, they focus on demographic factors. Of the total searches (N = 181.824), 1,728 (0.9%) were made for suicidal behavior. Average age 43.21 (±18) years and 57.4% were women. Zhao and Shai's study reveals that students' attitudes towards suicidal behavior and attitudes towards suicide survivors play as a mediator between self-efficacy and self-evaluations in managing happiness among college students. Therefore, for this population, attitudes towards suicide can be understood as one of the factors shaping self-assessment and life satisfaction.

Consequently, it is essential in this special issue to aim to improve knowledge

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about suicide by finding specific psychological characteristics that can ease targeted prevention, intervention methods and programs. Improving understanding of these issues can help clinicians and researchers create specific

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prevention strategies and methods that will ultimately help reduce suicide rates worldwide and find psychological relief for all those struggling with suicidal ideation and behavior.

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Causes of Suicidal Behavior

The causes of suicidal behavior are not fully understood; however, this behavior is clearly due to the complex interplay of many factors. Although many risk factors have been found, often not explaining why people try to end their lives, it explains important recent developments in the theoretical, clinical, and empirical science of psychology about the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors, and it is necessary to emphasize the crucial importance of psychological factors. Personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social aspects, and negative life events contribute significantly to suicidal behavior. Most people who struggle with suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek treatment.^[14]

Personality and Individual Differences

Although many risk factors have been found, they often do not explain why people try to end their lives. This explains important recent developments in the theoretical, clinical, and empirical science of psychology about the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors, and it is necessary to emphasize the vital importance of psychological factors. Personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social aspects, and negative life events are factors that contribute to suicidal behavior. Most people who struggle with suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek treatment. While some evidence suggests that different forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy may reduce the risk of suicide attempts, there is virtually no evidence of factors that protect against suicide. Urgent attention is needed to the development of innovative psychological and psychosocial treatments.

Risk Taking and Decision Making

Suicide is the 14th leading cause of death worldwide, responsible for 1.5% of all deaths. While psychological factors such as risk-taking and decision making can influence the risk of other causes of death (for example, heart disease and cancer), suicide is perhaps the most directly affected cause of death by psychological

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factors because a person makes an informed decision. His decision to end his own life points to this. Therefore, it is the responsibility of psychologists, psychiatrists, and relevant mental health professionals to understand suicide and develop

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methods to predict and prevent its occurrence. Earlier reports have supplied general assessments of the problem of suicidality and evaluate and synthesize current knowledge of the psychology of suicidal behavior, including psychological theories of suicidal behavior, risk and protective factors, and psychological interventions. It is to supply a summary of some of the most exciting and (in our opinion) important findings about the psychology of suicidal behavior.

Space constraints prevent us from taking part in the full breadth of psychological factors that can contribute to suicidal behavior and the full depth of what is now known. This is not a final and comprehensive report of available knowledge, but rather an introduction to the psychological factors involved in suicide.^[15] Prevalence estimates vary widely by country; however, once present, the characteristics of suicidal behavior are quite consistent in different countries. For example, the onset of suicidal ideation increases dramatically during adolescence in each country studied. About one-third of people who are considering suicide will go on to try suicide, and more than 60% of these transitions will occur within the first year after the first onset of suicidal ideation. This finding is consistent with the continuum approach, and the risk of suicide increases as the individual attempts to think and plan. Multifactorial causes and the role of psychiatric disorders the causes of suicidal behavior are not fully understood; however, this behavior is clearly due to the complex interplay of many varied factors. The risk of non-fatal suicidal behavior is increased in younger people, women (who have higher rates of non-fatal suicidality than men, but men are more likely to die by suicide), unmarried people, and people who commit suicide.

Although a number of risk factors have been found for suicidal behavior, suicide is when an individual deliberately ends their own life. Generally, the term suicidal behavior is used to refer to thoughts and behaviors related to an individual who intentionally ends their own life. These thoughts include the more specific consequences of suicidal ideation; this means deliberately considering ending one's own life; suicide plan, which refers to the formulation of a specific plan for the individual to end their own life; and suicide attempt refers to engaging in potentially self-harming behavior with at least some intention to die as a result of

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the behavior.[16]

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That is, it is not clear why the factors work together to increase the risk of this behavior. Perhaps the most studied risk factor for suicidal behavior is the earlier presence of a psychiatric disorder. Findings from psychological autopsy studies show that more than 90% of people who die by suicide have a psychiatric disorder before they die. For balance, however, most people with psychiatric disorders never commit suicide (that is, experience suicidal thoughts, try suicide, or die by suicide). For example, less than 5% of people hospitalized for treatment of a mood disorder die by suicide; Most people with psychiatric disorders will not die by suicide and will not experience suicidal behavior. Thus, although the presence and accumulation of psychiatric disorders are risk factors for suicidal behavior, they have little predictive power and, perhaps more importantly, do not explain why people try to kill themselves. Therefore, more specific markers of suicide risk need to be defined.

Suicidal Thoughts

The science of psychology is well placed to understand why some people try suicide while others do not. Understanding the psychological processes underlying both suicidal ideation and the decision to act on suicidal thoughts is particularly important because interventions should aim to address the first occurrence of suicidal ideation before going ahead to a suicide attempt.

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Psychological Theories of Suicidal Behavior

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The origins of recent theories can be traced back to Freud, but continued research into suicide did not begin in earnest until the 1950s and has grown significantly over the past 25 years. Contemporary models of suicide are mostly stress of origin and cognitive diathesis.[17] Recent cognitive and behavioral models have also guided treatment developments. Linehan's emotion regulation disorder model, originally developed in the context of borderline personality disorder, supported dialectical behavior therapy, while other theoretical developments focused on the individual's evaluation system. Psychological theories are important theoretically and clinically because they supply a framework for understanding how complex factors combine to increase suicide risk. Additionally, these theories help find potentially modifiable targets for therapy. Although earlier theories focused on individual psychological factors, they did not explain why most people with suicidal ideation do not try suicide. From a clinical point of view, the importance of being able to make predictions about suicidal transitions can be explained by the cubic suicide model, Shneidman (1985)9, the combination of pressure (stress), pain (psychic pain), and uneasiness can be explained by suicide risk.

Cognitive Vulnerability and Suicide as Self-Escape

Cognitive vulnerability (for example, social problem solving) explains the relationship between stress and suicide risk. Baumeister (1990) interprets the main motivation for suicide as escaping from painful self-awareness. The clinical model of suicidal behavior was summarized by Mann et al. (1999). Suicide risk is not only related to a psychiatric disorder (stressor) but also to another diathesis (i.e., a tendency to experience more suicidal thoughts or impulsivity).

Suicide mode as a cognitive behavioral model of suicide was summarized by Rudd et al (2001). Based on the ten principles of cognitive theory, the model describes cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and physiological system features associated with the development of suicide risk by Williams (2001). The risk of suicide increases when feelings of defeat and entrapment are high and the potential for recovery (eg, social support) is low.

Interpersonal-Psychological Model

Joiner (2005))15 The suicidal urge results from a high level of burden and inhibition of belonging.[18] An appraisal model suggesting that risk arises from the interaction between biases in information processing, schema, and evaluation systems is summarized by Wenzel and Beck (2008) as a cognitive model of suicidal behavior. The diathesis-stress model with three main structures: temperamental fragility factors, cognitive processes associated with psychiatric illness, and cognitive processes associated with suicidal actions should be included in these explanations.

The Different Activation Theory of Suicide

Williams et al. (2008) describes the relational network model. Experience of suicidal ideation or behavior during a depressive episode increases the likelihood of it reoccurring during later episodes. The integrated motivational-volitional model of suicidal behavior is a diathesis-stress model that decides the components of suicide. Pre-motivational, suicidal (thought and intention formation) and volitional (behavioral reenactment) phases adapted from O'Connor with permission from John Wiley & Sons.

Attempt or Until Death

From suicidal ideation to try or death, it is necessary to focus on two theories that do this. Indeed, it is particularly important to understand this distinction. First, Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide assumes the coexistence of prominent levels of perceived burden (i.e., feeling a burden to others) and low levels of belonging (i.e., feeling alienated or not), and being hopeless that these states will not change, suicidal desire (i.e., suicidal ideation) leads to the development of thought. Suicidal desire is a necessary reason, although not sufficient for a suicide attempt. However, if a person with a high suicidal desire gains the ability to attempt suicide, the risk of a serious suicide attempt increases.[19] According to the theory, exposure to and encountering previous painful experiences increases an individual's tolerance for the physical-painful aspects of self-harm through habit processes. Fundamental components of the theory have attracted a great deal of research attention. Second, the integrated motivational-volitional model of suicidal behavior conceptualizes suicide as a behavior (rather than a byproduct of mental disorders) that develops through motivational and volitional stages. The motivational stage finds the factors that govern the development of suicidal ideation and intention, while the volitional stage outlines the factors that decide whether an individual attempts suicide. This model integrates key factors from earlier theories into a detailed map of the suicide process, from thoughts to suicidal actions.[20]

Stressful, humiliating or defeating conditions are considered the most important within the integrated motivational-volitional model. When the individual feels both defeated and trapped, the likelihood of suicidal ideation increases when motivational modifiers (for example, low social levels) are present. The integrated motivational-volitional model draws on pioneering research by Williams et al. on social-order theory, the cry of pain and arrested flight hypotheses, the differentiation activation hypothesis, and the theory of planned behavior. While interpersonal suicidality theory assumes that bought ability generates behavioral action (i.e., suicidal attempts), this is only one of several (volitional stages) factors within the integrated motivational-volitional model proposed to increase the likelihood of suicidal attempts. Such factors include exposure to the suicidal behavior of others, impulsivity, and access to suicide tools. Although the integrated motivational-volitional model is new, empirical evidence supports its usefulness.

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Psychological Risk and Protective Factors

Factors associated with suicide risk can be classified into four groups:

1. *personality and individual differences,*
2. *cognitive factors,*
3. *social factors and*
4. *negative life events.*

In reviewing these factors, we summarize what is known to date, but do not fully describe the potential mechanisms by which these factors may influence suicidal behavior, an extremely important target for future research. We chose these factors because they were implicated in theoretical models, attracted research attention in the literature, or were promising candidates for the future.[21] Personality and individual differences Factors related to personality and individual differences are of interest because they are fairly stable in adulthood, often have a known biological basis, are influenced by the environment, and affect cognition and emotion. Although hopelessness is often operationalized as a situation factor (i.e., a time-varying factor), we include it in this section to highlight that it also has trait components (i.e., components that are relatively stable over time), and future research will explore relative versus situational hopelessness. predict predictive usefulness. Hopelessness, defined as pessimism about the future, is a strong predictor of all indicators of suicidal ideation and behavior. In a classic study, Beck and colleagues were able to predict 91% of all suicides due to blocked belonging.[22]

However, findings from a 12-year prospective Finnish study showed that hopelessness was a non-significant predictor of suicide compared with hopelessness (in a sample of 224 suicide attempts). More recently, in a small study of suicidal attempters, hopelessness did not significantly predict future suicide attempts at a 4-year follow-up when history of suicide attempts and entrapment were included in the analysis. These more recent mixed findings suggest that while hopelessness is important in the development of suicidal ideation (consistent with theoretical models), other factors may be more useful in predicting actual suicide

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attempts or deaths. Although impulsivity has been studied for decades, the association with suicide risk is not as consistent or straightforward as originally thought, and its impact may be less direct. Findings from many studies have

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shown that self-reported impulsivity is associated with suicidal ideation, suicide attempts, and suicide deaths. or cognitive impulsivity. Other research emphasizes the importance of differentiation. Again, between impulsivity as a trait and a situation construct, the evidence is mixed as to whether impulsivity is related to the medical severity of the event. However, impulsivity should still be considered when assessing the risk of suicide or self-harm. It may not be significant in all cases of suicide risk, but it is more likely to be clear in the young than in the elderly. Impulsivity may be useful in predicting recurrent suicide attempts in individuals with personality disorders.

Aggression is associated with suicide attempts. Negative urgency, defined as the degree to which a person acts recklessly when distressed, also needs more research.

perfectionism

Increasing evidence suggests that perfectionism is associated with suicidal ideation and suicide attempts, but few prospective clinical studies have been conducted. Perfectionism can be defined in separate ways and is not equally associated with the risk of all types of suicide. One type of socially determined perfectionism is defined as the belief that other people [for example, family members] have unrealistically grand expectations of you, particularly when these socially determined beliefs are most consistently associated with suicidal thoughts and attempts, when internalized as self-confidence. Recent research suggests that social dimensions of perfectionism increase suicide risk by promoting a sense of social disconnection, which is consistent with the integrated motivational-volitional model and the interpersonal theory of suicide.[23] The big five personality dimensions: neuroticism, extraversion, agreeableness, openness to experience, and conscientiousness are generally associated with high neuroticism and low extraversion with suicidal ideation, attempts, and completions. However, there are exceptions; In the 18-year follow-up of depressed patients, neuroticism did not predict future suicide risk. The joint effects of high neuroticism and low extraversion may be stronger predictors of suicide than neuroticism alone. The proposed interaction is consistent with dominant theories suggesting that people are more susceptible to stress (i.e., high neuroticism) and socially disconnected.[24]

Pre-Motivational Stage

Background factors and triggering events include thoughts of defeat and humiliation, and suicidal intent. Examples include social problem solving, coping, memory biases, and ruminative processes:

artistic belonging, burden, future thoughts, goals, norms, social support, and attitudes

Frequently Reviewed Topics

Findings about openness to experience, conscientiousness, and agreeableness are less consistent and these constructs have been examined less often.

Optimism and resilience

Surprisingly, few attempts have been made to investigate the direct or indirect relationship between persistent optimism and suicidal ideation or attempts, and almost no longitudinal studies have been published. However, some evidence in college students suggests that people with high optimism have a reduced risk of suicidal ideation or try when faced with serious or moderately negative life events, compared with people with low optimism. Optimism has also been shown to keep the relationship between hopelessness and suicidal ideation. The protective effect of optimism was also proved in a sample of patients from a primary care clinic. While these findings are promising, the protective effect over time is largely unknown and needs further investigation. Despite research into resilience(“It is defined as “the qualities that enable a person to be successful in the face of difficulties”).[25] Some evidence suggests that resilience has a protective effect on suicidal ideation in military personnel, alcohol and illicit drug abusers, and prisoners, but its effect on suicide attempts or deaths by suicide is largely unknown.

Validation of the suicide resilience inventory may encourage further research on this topic. Considering the scarcity of research on protective factors, efforts have been made to find factors that supply resilience by resisting the risk of suicide in the face of difficulties. Such studies have examined the assessment of stressful situations and self-assessment.

Evaluations may be protective against the development of suicidal ideation. To understand how and why cognitive factors cause some people's thought processes to decide to end their lives, researchers examined different cognitive processes that may be inadequate or dysfunctional. Such studies have found several cognitive factors that appear to increase the risk of suicidal behavior.

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For decades, clinical and theoretical explanations have described suicidal people as cognitively rigid or inflexible, leading to the conclusion that suicide is the only choice. Findings from studies in which behavioral tests of cognitive rigidity were

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applied to those who tried suicide and from clinical controls supported this view. This rigidity was first reported in an early study by Neuringer and has since been proved multiple times using a set of neuropsychological measures of cognitive rigidity or flexibility, such as set-change tests (i.e., the ability to change), when changes in thinking and behavior are seen in response to a changing environment. Findings from recent studies have shown that this effect is not explained by the presence of depression and cognitive rigidity predicts suicidal ideation prospectively. It is also clear in impaired decision making, those who try suicide.[26]

A review of the relationship between rumination and suicidal behavior decides the relationship between the findings and the main psychological risk and protective factors for suicidal ideation and suicidal behavior:

1. *Personality and individual differences*
2. *Despair*
3. *impulsivity*
4. *perfectionism*
5. *neuroticism and extraversion*
6. *Optimism*
7. *Flexibility Cognitive factors*
8. *cognitive rigidity*
9. *rumination*
10. *thought suppression*
11. *Autobiographical memory biases*
12. *Belonging and being a burden*
13. *Fear of injury and death*
14. *insensitivity to pain*
15. *Problem solving and coping*

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16. *Agitation*
17. *implicit associations*

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18. *Attentional biases*
19. *future thought*
20. *Goal setting*
21. *reasons to live*
22. *Defeat and entrapment social factors*
23. *social contagion*
24. *Modelling*
25. *Infection*
26. *gay homophily*
27. *Exposure to death by suicide of others*
28. *Social Isolation Adverse life events*
29. *Troubles in childhood*
30. *Traumatic life events in adulthood*
31. *physical illness*
32. *All other interpersonal stressors*
33. *Psychophysiological stress response*

Causes of a Person's Symptoms

A distinction has been noted between reflective rumination, in which a person dwells on their symptoms, and reflective thinking, in which a person considers the causes of their symptoms and possible solutions.[27] Rumination has also been associated with increased symptoms of depression, hopelessness, and impaired problem solving; An important goal for future research is to clarify how these factors may work together to increase the risk of suicidal behavior. Thought suppression refers to deliberate attempts to stop thinking unwanted thoughts. Over the past 25 years, Wegner and other researchers have reported that thought suppression paradoxically increases the frequency of certain unwanted thoughts and may be a mechanism for the development of various forms of psychopathology.

Findings from assorted studies have shown that the tendency to suppress unwanted thoughts is associated with both suicidal ideation and attempts, and thought suppression mediates the relationship between emotion reactivity and the emergence of self-harming thoughts and behaviors.

Autobiographical memory biases Suicidal behavior has a reduced ability to recall certain autobiographical memories, which may impair their ability to imagine the future and effectively solve problems, thereby increasing the likelihood of suicidal behavior.

Abuse and Affective Disorders

Some evidence suggests that autobiographical biographical memory biases result in part from earlier abuse or the presence of an affective disorder, and thus represent a potential mechanism by which abuse, and affective disorders can lead to suicidal behavior. Finally, this suggested that Joiner belonging could be avoided. It is aimed at the development of suicidal thoughts and behaviors. Consistent with these theories, subjective feeling of lack of social connection and inhibition of belonging was associated with suicidal ideation and suicide attempts.

The feeling of being a burden to others is an independent predictor of suicidal ideation in a society. For a sample range, including older adults, and people with chronic pain, perceived burdensome has also been shown to mediate the relationship between perfectionism and suicidal ideation, and continued to predict thought even after controlling for factors such as depression and hopelessness.

Consistent with the interpersonal theory of suicide, the interaction of perceived belonging and burden is predictive of suicidal ideation even after controlling for depressive symptoms. Fearlessness and insensitivity to pain Since suicidal behavior often involves inflicting physical pain on the body, suicide risk and both pain sensitivity and tolerance and fearlessness of death have been studied. Although almost all research on pain sensitivity has focused on non-suicidal self-harm, increased pain thresholds and tolerance have been reported in suicidal adolescents.

changes in pain sensitivity, suicidal ideation or suicidal ideation or behavior;

The issue of how these changes change as a function of the suicide history and throughout life needs to be clarified. Research findings reveal that those who try suicide show higher fearlessness of injury and death than controls who do not commit suicide, and this difference may explain why men are more likely to die by suicide than women.

Problem solving and coping Attempting to kill themselves have difficulties with problem solving or coping, perhaps overt. Still, research findings have consistently shown a link between suicidal behavior and deficits in both interpersonal problem solving and coping. However, given the cross-sectional nature of most studies on this topic, the direction of this relationship is unclear. Also, these relationships seem to be mostly explained by the presence of depression.

Agitation, often conceptualized as a state of anxious excitement or disinhibition, has been associated with suicidal behavior in many studies. For example, in one chart study of 76 patients who died by suicide on admission, 79% had severe anxiety or agitation shortly before their death. Agitation has been hypothesized to be one of the potential mechanisms by which bipolar disorder, medical illness, and the prescription of certain psychiatric drugs may increase patient exposure.

Recent research suggests that agitation predicts suicide attempts, especially in people with high suicidality. Implicit associations suggest an implicit mental relationship between death and self, and people with a recent history of suicidal behavior. Findings in research using the implicit association test this association differentiated suicidal attempters from distressed people who did not try emergency psychiatric treatment (i.e., suicide attempters responded faster when matching death and self-related stimuli than they did [measured in milliseconds]).

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Perhaps more importantly, this mental association with death calls for further investigation as it predicts future suicide attempts by clinicians or patients. If a recent history of suicidal behavior shows greater attention or interference with

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suicidal stimuli (for example, suicidal attempters take longer to name the color of suicidal words than neutral or negative words), and this bias is associated with the presence of a mood disorder and future judgment by clinicians or patients. predicts future suicide tries beyond other factors, including prior knowledge of suicidal behavior. However, it stays unclear whether attentional bias and implicit associations are caused by suicidal thoughts or are causes of suicidal thoughts. Future thinking and goal setting Since the 1990s, pessimism about the future (characterized by the absence of positive thoughts) has been associated with suicidal ideation and attempts. This effect of disrupting positive future thinking is independent of depression.

Future research will decide whether positive future thought and suicide attempts change over time and whether the content of positive future thought influences the degree to which positive thoughts are protective. A more detailed study of the images and going forward (i.e., images of carrying out future suicide plans or being dead) is also promising. The pursuit of personal goals defines identity, and how people adapt when a goal becomes unattainable is known to affect well-being. Indeed, the evidence suggests that suicidal attempters who tend not to reattach to new goals (versus current unattainable goals) are at higher risk of rehospitalization after harming themselves and are more affected by the extent of detachment from the current goal.

Reasons to Live

It has been extensively studied and incorporated into treatment protocols in the prediction of suicidal ideation and attempts. Evidence suggests that individuals who have several reasons to live are at increased risk of suicidal ideation and attempts. Regarding reasons to live, a 10-year follow-up study found that psychiatric outpatients with a moderate-to-strong will to die and little will to live were at increased risk of suicide. Defeat and entrapment have received considerable attention in social class theories of depression, in the scientific literature on arrested flight, and more recently in the integrated motivational-volitional model. The inability to escape defeat or stressful conditions supplies the environment for suicidal thoughts to occur. While defeat and entrapment are good, the fixed structures in the Psychopathology literature offer important hope for applications in suicide research. Indeed, both defeat and entrapment distinguish suicidal individuals from controls, independent of depression and hopelessness, and both predict suicidal ideation and tries over time. The trap has also been shown to predict repeated suicide attempts over a 4-year period beyond traditional risk markers.

Social factors

Suicide does not happen in a social vacuum. A family history of suicide increases the risk of suicide; this effect is independent of a family history of mental disorders and thus suggests a partial social transference effect. Exposure to suicidal behavior by family or friends is also associated with these behaviors in adolescents. Mother's suicidal behavior may be more strongly associated with spring suicidal behavior than father's suicidal behavior, and children are more likely to be influenced by parents. suicidal behavior is more common than in adolescents or adults. The effects on suicide risk following suicidal grief are discussed in detail by Pitman and colleagues. Although psychological mechanisms (eg, modeling effects) need more experimental research, media depictions of suicide may affect suicide rates.

The Effect of the Internet on Suicidal Behavior

The impact of the Internet on suicidal behavior requires further attention, as it can have both negative (for example, discouraging help-seeking) and positive (for example, support resource or signage) effects. Indeed, research findings have shown that approximately 20% of adolescents report that the internet or social networking sites influence their self-harm decisions. Psychological processes (including contagion, imitation, suggestion, identification, social learning, and classificatory homophily or susceptibility) also play a role in the development of suicidal clusters. Social isolation and lack of social support are set up correlates of suicide risk and are important components of contemporary models of suicidal behavior. Any risk of suicide should naturally assess how socially isolated a vulnerable individual is. Adverse life events, childhood adversities, the occurrence of adverse life events in childhood (for example, physical, sexual, and emotional abuse; domestic violence; and parental illness, divorce, or death) followed by the experience of suicidal behavior are a subject of separate study. These study findings proved a strong dose-response relationship between the number of adverse events and the risk of later suicide attempts. Childhood sexual and physical abuse is a particularly strong risk.[\[28\]](#)

Sequence factors for both the onset and persistence of suicidal behavior and the risk of suicidal behavior are especially high in childhood and adolescence, and the relationship between childhood adversities and suicidal behavior decreases with age.

Traumatic Cases

Unfortunately, adverse life events can affect well-being at any age, and traumatic events in adulthood (for example, physical or sexual abuse; death of a loved one; disasters or accidents; exposure to war or other violence) may also increase.^[29] Study findings showed a dose-response relationship between the number of adverse events and the risk of subsequent suicidal behavior; again, physical and sexual abuse seem to carry the highest risk for both the onset and persistence of suicidal behavior.

Physical Illness

Physical illnesses are also linked to suicidal behavior. The presence and accumulation of physical diseases (eg, heart disease, chronic pain, and respiratory disorders) are significantly associated with later suicidal behavior. The mechanism by which physical illness increases the risk of suicidal behavior is not fully understood. While some research findings suggest that this relationship can be attributed to the presence of depression, other researchers reported that this relationship persisted even after controlling for mental disorders.

Other Interpersonal Stressors

After various interpersonal stressors control the risk of suicidal behavior and even the effects of mental disorders, interpersonal stressors can take various forms and several diverse types of stressors have been associated with suicidal behavior, including romantic problems, legal difficulties, loss of income, non-straight orientation and bullying, victimization. While the link between significant adverse life events and an increased risk of suicidal behavior is clear, the mechanism is not fully understood. While some researchers report that the relationship between negative life events and suicidal behavior is mediated by the presence of mental disorders, other study findings do not support this explanation. A psychophysiological mechanism probably supports the basis of this relationship. Indeed, dysregulation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis plays a role in the suicidal process. However, the precise nature of the association is unclear, as evidence suggests that suicide risk is associated with abnormal cortisol concentrations or a maladaptive cortisol response to stress. Moreover, most people experience some type of negative life event at some point in their lives, but do not engage in suicidal behavior; this highlights the importance of considering how vulnerability factors and stressors might interact to produce suicidal behavior, as theoretical models suggest.

Psychological Treatment

Most people (roughly 60%) who struggle with suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek treatment. The main reasons for not seeking help are low perceived need and desire to take the problem personally. It connects people with suicidal thoughts and behaviors with effective treatments. Unfortunately, few proven evidence-based treatments for suicidal behavior exist, such as prevention programs, pharmacological interventions, and psychological treatments. Treatments that target depression have not been shown to reduce suicidal thoughts or behaviors. Some evidence suggests that certain forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy that directly target suicidal thoughts and behaviors may reduce the risk of re-attempts in people who have tried suicide. Foreexample, clinical trials testing dialectical behavioral therapy (in patients with borderline personality disorder) and cognitive therapy (in those who have recently attempted suicide) have supplied support for the effectiveness of these treatments to reduce the rate of suicide reattempts compared to others.

Basic Guidelines for Future Psychological Research

Understanding and Prediction

A consensus on terminology and phenomenology is necessary for all self-harming behavior. It requires larger-scale studies testing psychological models and risk factors to predict suicide attempt and death. Incorporating psychological factors, national link databases, and psychological autopsy studies are essential. A better understanding of the factors that distinguish suicide attempts from those who are serious about it and those who have repeatedly tried suicide is necessary to integrate experimental, natural, clinical, and non-clinical research findings. Comprehensive testing is essential in investigating psychological models.

Suicidal Behavior

Focusing on the psychological factors that protect against suicidal behavior requires a separate effort. A better understanding of the psychology of method choice is needed. Further research in psychology is essential in lifelong participants from different ethnicities and countries.

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Intervention and Prevention

Larger and sufficiently strong clinical studies are essential. Psychological treatment trials are necessary to reduce suicidal ideation, attempts, and suicide. The development of more innovative brief psychosocial interventions (using a range of delivery methods) to reduce suicidal ideation, attempts, and suicide increases the risk of suicidal and self-harming suicidal behavior and suicidal clusters. A better understanding of the barriers to seeking help is important. Integrating advances in psychological science into suicide prevention and intervention programs and developing public health interventions to foster resilience is important for low-income and middle-income countries as well as the development of interventions.

However, several replicates have been made by independent research groups, and studies have yet to find predetermined interventions. With regard to preventing people at risk from attempting suicide, findings from a meta-analysis of cognitive behavioral therapies for suicidal behavior showed a statistically significant effect of cognitive behavioral therapy for reducing the rate of suicide attempts; however, the researchers demonstrate a publication bias in this regard, with smaller studies reporting more positive effect sizes and no published study findings showing negative effects for any intervention, like a funnel plot of published studies with near-zero centers. Collaborative assessment and management of suicide is a clinical intervention designed to improve the therapeutic alliance and reduce the risk of suicidal behavior. Restricting access to lethal pathways is also welcome in terms of safety planning interventions that include the identification of warning signs, coping strategies and support resources. Mentalization-based therapy has shown some promise for reducing self-harm in adolescents.

Most Suicidal People Do Not Get Treatment and Little Evidence Is Available for Suicide

The effectiveness of the interventions received highlights the enormous importance of future work to develop psychological treatments for people at risk for suicidal behavior. The utility of the Internet and smartphones in treatment delivery also requires close examination. Basic guidelines for psychological research Despite significant advances in the understanding of the suicidal mind, much more psychological research is needed. Suicide studies should routinely include psychological components, especially when it comes to large-scale nationally linked studies of suicide and suicide attempts.

Psychological Autopsy Studies

Psychological autopsy studies, which collected information about the deceased from several informants, have played a significant role in understanding the risk factors for suicide. More complex autopsy studies should be conducted in the future to investigate psychological factors in more detail.[30] Studies using new technologies (eg, smartphones) and real-time data collection (eg, ecological snapshots) are important in this regard. Focusing on the differential effects of psychological factors on suicide risk as a function of age, culture, and ethnicity should be increased. There is still a tendency to generalize findings to, for example, older adult and adolescent populations from mid-adulthood. Researchers also relied heavily on self-report observational studies; multi-method approaches, with an increasing focus on basic science experimental research, will help uncover the mechanisms by which factors increase or decrease suicide risk. As the ability develops, testing of psychological theories of suicide risk should be the rule rather than the exception. Such programmed testing of risk and protective factors will not only help researchers but will also aid clinicians in translating research into clinical practice. Physical availability (i.e., access) to methods of suicide affects their use, but not much.

It is important to have information about the psychological factors that affect the preference of one suicide method over another. Although 60% of the world's suicides occur in Asia, psychological suicide is still dominated by research in populations in Western Europe, the USA, and Canada. The lack of research on protective factors also needs to be addressed. While the development and use of psychological treatments has increased somewhat, they are not sufficiently supported by the evidence and most people who experience suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek them out. Barriers to seeking help and the role of the media (including social media) in the suicide process are also poorly understood; Although there are media guidelines on suicide reports, more empirical evidence is needed on which aspects of reporting are most dangerous. Finally, psychological science has a lot to offer policy planners in the development and implementation of suicide prevention programs. Promising multi-part intervention developments have been made in recent years and further progress is needed to tackle this devastating public health challenge.

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Suicide is a public health problem of paramount importance given its lasting devastating effects on families, friends, and communities.[31]

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Empirically Validated Interventions

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Country-specific empirically validated interventions should be informed by evidence-based research. Yet, compared to the depth of knowledge on suicide, risk, and prevention in the western world (Bridge, Goldstein, & Brent, 2006; Fontenella et al., 2015; Van Geel, Vedder, & Tanilon, 2014), the relative paucity of research on suicide in Africa (Adinkrah, et al. 2011; Osafo, Akotia and Boakye, 2016); Although there have been some efforts to shed light on the phenomenon in the last decade in Ghana (Adinkrah, 2011; Osafo, Hjelmeland, Akotia, & Knizek, 2011), it is noteworthy.[32]

It is difficult to learn about completed suicides. Hence, the increasing concentration of research on finding risk factors for suicidal ideation and attempts (Osman et al., 1998). While reliable and official statistics on suicide among university students in Ghana are lacking, some studies supply insight into the risks for better understanding of events among this group. Quarshie et al. (2019) supplied basic information about suicide among nursing and midwifery students. Other studies, not focusing specifically on suicidal behavior, have found worrying prevalence rates (mild, moderate, and severe), inadequate social support, substance abuse, self-stigmatization, and traumatic life events among college students (Andoh-Arthur, Oppong Asante, & Osafo, 2015; Oppong Asante & Andoh-Arthur, 2015). Anxiety, loneliness, poor self-esteem, anger management problems (Peltzer, Kleintjes, Wyk, Thompson, & Mashego, 2008) and academic difficulties that ultimately hinder subjective well-being have also been found (Oppong Asante, Kugbey, Osafo, Quarshie, & Sarfo, 2017) and potentially the occurrence of psychological distress and poor mental health as contributors to suicidal behavior.

Protective Factors

Evidence for protective factors includes good social support, self-esteem, and keeping healthy and positive relationships (Sarchiapone, Mandelli, Iosue, Andrisano, & Roy, 2011; WHO, 2014). Parental commitment and understanding (Borowski, Taliaferro, & McMorris, 2013; Opong Asante et al., 2017) and respect for students' privacy have protective effects. Religious affiliation and beliefs have also been found to positively reduce the risk of suicidal behavior among at-risk youth.

Suicidal ideation among university students is undoubtedly a multifaceted phenomenon with globally recognized negative and harmful effects on families, friends and even the socio-economic development of the countries in which it occurs. Among youth, particularly college students, suicide is the second leading cause of death alongside self-injury, placing this population at risk, and the importance of research to better understand the threat cannot be overemphasized.

Theoretically, this study examines suicide from the perspective of the human ecological model to understand the occurrence of suicide among university students.

While dissolving the buffers as well as the risks of suicide can be complex, the model offers the conceptualization of suicide from a multifaceted approach integrating individual, social, and familial factors that may be associated with suicide occurrence, thus supplying a broader environmental context interpretation for better understanding and clarification of risk factors. Therefore, the two-pronged specific aims of the study were to decide the lifetime and current prevalence of suicidal ideation or attempts; It is necessary to find the associated risks and protective factors. Based on the available literature, the study predicts that students who report higher levels of psychological distress but have lower levels of self-esteem and subjective well-being will be more likely to show suicidal behaviors (here, ideas and/or attempts). In other words, a negative relationship between suicidal ideation or try and these variables is expected. Likewise, students with low self-esteem are expected to be less satisfied with their lives and to experience more psychological distress. As greater subjective well-being is associated with a feeling of greater control over important life choices, a greater subjective well-being is expected to protect against suicidal thoughts.

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The study is in a cross-sectional design as it aims to set up a possible relationship between various variables.

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A Global Health and Social Issue

Suicide is a global health and social problem, and an estimated 800,000 people die by suicide each year. The social and psychological costs of suicide are high. It is estimated that for each suicide, six to 20 people, usually family members and acquaintances of the deceased, are negatively affected psychologically and emotionally. This phenomenon has been described as 'suicidal exposure'. It is the impact of exposure to suicide on these two professional groups (mental health professionals and first responders) that underpins this scoping review. These groups differ from bereaved family and friends in that they are more likely to commit suicide than usual, as well as the professional nature of their relationship with the person who died by suicide. Mental health professionals and first responders will, in most cases, be uninterested in the deceased and unlikely to have a social or personal relationship with them. Yet these two professional groups differ from each other in that mental health professionals often have formed a therapeutic alliance with the person who has died by suicide, and first responders are often unknown to the individual prior to suicide. Because the nature of the relationship with the person who died by suicide for mental health professionals is different from that of first responders, we might expect the effect of suicidal exposure on these two groups to be different.

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder

Mental health professionals (especially psychiatrists) and first responders themselves also have high suicide rates. One explanation for the higher suicide rates among these occupations is higher levels of occupational psychological distress and work-related Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) for first responders. In the literature, psychological distress is often referred to as indirect trauma or compassion fatigue. Indirect trauma or work-related emotional transition, defined as the distortion of feelings and thoughts caused by the transmission of traumatic experiences while cumulatively seeing disturbing clinical material, can have both personal and professional implications. On a personal level, VT is characterized by sleep disturbances, feelings of hopelessness, and disconnection from others.

One of the contributors to higher levels of psychological distress and VT among mental health professionals and first responders may be higher rates of suicide. A recent systematic review suggests a link between psychological distress experienced in these occupations and higher suicide rates.[\[33\]](#)

Exposure to suicide can personally affect first responders and mental health professionals and affect their professional practice. Changes in professional practice after a patient's suicide include increased awareness of suicide risk, decreased confidence, and more restrictive practices, including increased monitoring and detention for nurses. Management of suicidal behavior in patients may manifest as increased alertness when assessing suicide, or systematic referral of a patient to another colleague (for a second evaluation), or complete avoidance of treating patients at risk for suicide.

Other professional outcomes include questioning confidence in career choice, which may affect professional persistence. Regarding the reassessment of career choices, questioning one's career choice is not limited to health professionals and has been seen in other professions dealing with emotionally sensitive content, such as suicide researchers.

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For first responders, emotional effects include high emotional labor (the process of controlling emotions compared to organizational, and task demands) that has been found to be associated with increased suicidal ideation among

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firefighters. This group of professionals are often the first to be involved in a suspected suicide event, which is described as one of the most critical and traumatic situations first responders can meet during their work. There is little discussion in the literature about strategies for managing psychological distress from suicidal exposure among first responders as a professional group.

While research to date has supplied some insight into the complex effects of suicide exposure on mental health professionals, limited research has been done on the impact of suicide exposure on first responders. In addition, this literature has not been reviewed together as a case of occupational-based suicide exposure and its effects.[\[34\]](#)

Emotional responses described by professionals included sadness, shock, surprise, blame, despair, guilt, self-doubt, grief, and anger. His professional responses ranged from increased awareness of suicide risk, decreased professional confidence, fear of publicity and lawsuits, increased referrals to psychiatrists, and workplace sadness.

Psychologists and Psychiatrists

Eight of the eleven articles examining the effects of suicidal exposure reported the prevalence of patient suicide focusing on psychologists and psychiatrists, with 31.5–92% of these professionals having experienced at least one client suicide. In addition, Gibbons et al. (2019) found that 72% of patients died due to more than one suicide, 15% experienced more than six patients and 3% experienced more than ten patient suicides. Rothes et al. (2013) also found that male psychologists and psychiatrists had more patient suicides than their female counterparts. But the researchers did not explain this difference.

The most common emotional response reported among psychologists and psychiatrists was sadness, and shock, guilt, self-doubt, low mood, psychological pain, and fear were also reported. Female psychiatrists and psychologists reported higher distress effects than males. Another gender difference was related to feelings of responsibility for death, with women reporting slightly higher scores (mean = 49.9, SD = 23.2) than men (mean = 38.8, SD = 25.5) for feeling responsible at the time of death. Gender and responsibility of the deceased patient were significantly associated with emotional impact. Female professionals and those who felt more responsible for the patient's death had more pronounced emotional reactions at once after a patient's suicide. Studies found that female psychiatrists reported significantly more feelings of failure and defeat (31%) than men (10%), but no other difference in terms of gender, and found that although male professionals experienced more patient suicides, women reported greater emotional impact than men. The gender differences presented in these articles are assumed without questioning why these differences are reported. This may reinforce the view that female psychiatrists and psychologists are more vulnerable to influences than their male counterparts and reproduce sexist views. The results should be questioned considering that male professionals may be less inclined to report emotional reactions and therefore report lower levels of emotional effects.

Overall, the most common professional response to exposure to suicide was increased awareness of suicide risk in patients. Other responses included increased use of suicidality assessment tools, attention to patients at risk, and increased attention to legal aspects of the therapeutic relationship. Peer support and

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information retrieval was the most widespread support looked for by these professionals after a patient's suicide.

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No studies have reported measures of suicide risk among psychologists and psychiatrists exposed to suicide. In addition, none of the studies of psychologists and psychiatrists have evaluated the relationship between exposure to suicide and their own risk of suicidal thoughts and behavior. These findings highlight how current research focuses on risk management and professional influences, not personal and emotional ones. As such, it seems to ignore psychologists and psychiatrists as potentially more at risk of suicide.

Only one study was conducted on mental health nurses. Nurses reported experiencing deep sadness, anger, frustration, and feelings of blame by other staff after a patient's suicide. Some nurses also said that they felt angry and resentful when they perceived the suicide attempt to attract attention. Many nurses felt anxiety, stress, restlessness, and fear because of feeling responsible for not being able to prevent suicide. The most common professional change was nurses' increased awareness of suicide risk among patients.

Counselors and Social Workers

The only article among counselors and social workers (USA) reporting the effects of suicide exposure reported that 82.7% of the sample was a patient attempt or complete suicide. The emotional effects reported were related to the news of suicide and fear of being sued, 19.8% reported distress after the suicide press release, and 44.5% of professionals were distressed by the prospect of litigation. This led professionals to consider changing careers (34.2%) and retiring early (15%). Peer support is the type of support most sought after and often described as helpful. Burnout and compassion fatigue were outcomes after suicidal exposure, with over 42.5% of suicides affecting scoring between moderate and extremely high for compassion. These findings relate to the fact that these professionals may have less training in mental health and suicide prevention than other professional categories.

The sample size of the studies ranged from 61 to 1,027 and all web-based questionnaires were used. The prevalence of being exposed to suicide while on duty (including suicidal behaviors) ranged from 34.8% to 92.4%. Hom, Stanley reported the prevalence of suicide exposure (74%) in firefighters' personal lives rather than while on duty. For those who knew someone who died by suicide, 54% reported that the deceased was another firefighter (but not a close colleague) and 31.1% reported that the deceased was a firefighter (a close professional colleague). 39% of those who reported having been exposed to suicide during their personal lives said "that he was affected by suicide" but "He stated that it was not at a level that would turn my life upside down. Two studies did not report the type of emotional reactions firefighters experience. Hom, Stanley are the only authors to report data on emotional responses. They found that a greater emotional impact of suicide exposure was associated with a statistically significant higher lifetime risk of suicide attempt, suicide risk, depressive symptoms, nightmares, insomnia, and more severe PTSD symptoms.

Similarly, Kimbrel et al. reported that the death of another firefighter or colleague of suicidal behavior was common among firefighters and had a significant impact on them. However, exposure to suicide only during the seizure was associated with an increased risk of suicide in these firefighters.

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In terms of the link between suicidal exposure and risk of suicidal behavior, Stanley et al reported that firefighters who took part in a suicide call were more likely to report suicidal ideation and attempts. No papers reported the professional effects of suicidal exposure on firefighters.

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police officers

Two articles, both from the USA, focused on police, one qualitative (n = 8) and the other collecting data via web survey (n = 813) (Cerel et al., 2019; Koch, 2010). Only one article reported the prevalence of suicide exposure. 95% of Law Enforcement Officers (LEOs) reported having met suicide while on duty. In this study, 70.7% of the sample reported a high rate of suicide (defined as having committed 10 or more suicides over their entire career). In addition, 73.4% reported that they knew someone who died because of suicide from their private life. The higher the level of on-duty suicide exposure, the more likely officers were to report a PTSD diagnosis, suggesting that taking part in suicide scenes had a specific PTSD effect.

Koch classified the coping strategies of police officers with the impact of the suicide scene. But research has not explored all extensions of these strategies, as they may be adaptive or maladaptive and therefore lead to varying risks for mental health outcomes. An in-depth exploration of these strategies will be valuable for understanding and designing interventions.

Police officers have the highest exposure to suicide, followed by firefighters, psychiatrists, counselors, social workers, and psychologists the lowest. No study has reported patient suicide among nurses. Most studies were conducted in the USA, other studies UK, Australia, Ireland, France, Belgium, Italy No research from other countries All articles evaluating suicide exposure used web surveys.

For most groups, the effects of exposure to suicide have been reported in the personal and professional domains. Personal effects were examined, with a focus on emotional responses, particularly shock and sadness. The lack of reporting all affective effects can be explained by the lack of qualitative research in this area, which, due to its subjective nature, may be more proper to investigate this phenomenon. In addition, most of the studies evaluating emotional impacts in this review used the Acute Emotional Impact Scale or an adaptation of this scale, participants may experience a much wider range of emotional responses such as

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frustration, anxiety, and others with only the emotional items made possible on the scale, although the use of the scales does not report such emotions. limits its expression and expression.

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The professional responses described showed that suicide risk and increased awareness of suicide cues were the most common effects on professional practice. Although we anecdotally expect nurses to change their practices after a patient's suicide, no article reported professional responses among nurses, firefighters, and police.

Qualitative studies tended to explore coping strategies used by professionals. Qualitative research has also shown that mental health professionals have an increased fear of suing after a patient's suicide. The critical incident review of safety procedures taken by professionals prior to suicide has been reported to be a distressing event, potentially worsening the effects of exposure to suicide.

An interesting finding from the review is that mental health professionals do not have self-assessments of mental health and suicide.[35] The lack of data on mental health outcomes makes it impossible to compare the effects of exposure to the effects of suicide on mental health professionals with those of first responders. We do not have data showing which profession is most affected by suicide. The lack of studies targeting mental health outcomes after suicide suggests that suicide researchers may not pay enough attention to suicide risk among health professionals and may be better equipped because they are trained to supply support in these situations. The recent review by Dutheil Aubert highlighted the lack of research examining the etiology and transition from suicidal ideation to suicide attempt among healthcare professionals. Therefore, we suggest that exposure to suicide should be considered as a risk factor as more research is needed to examine the link between exposure and suicidality among first responders.

This scoping review highlights some of the gaps in the research foundation about exposure to suicide in mental health professionals and first responders. First, there was a complete lack of research on exposure to suicide among paramedics and ambulance workers. Two reviews suggested that taking part in suicide is an emotional burden, with no article focused solely on exposure to suicide. In

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addition, there were only two studies examining police and three studies examining firefighters, all from the United States. There is a need for research that

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addresses the issue of exposure to suicide among these professionals and focuses on its emotional and occupational effects.

Second, validated scales are not used to assess emotional effects. Like Séguin, Bordeleau's review, according to this review, articles using the Event Impact Scale or a subscale of it also used the tool to set cutoff scores to categorize clinical distress levels or classify them as a surrogate. Following Bordeleau's discussion, Séguin does not report any cut-off points for the scale to categorize authors, so use of the scale may lead to the inflated result that professionals are clinically distressed. Future research should use appropriately validated scales to assess emotional distress to find those who are clinically affected and who may receive help from support.

Third, our review highlights the lack of qualitative research in this area. While quantitative research allows for hypothesis testing, qualitative in-depth research into the effects of suicidal exposure is necessary to quantify the phenomenon and better understand how the correlations subjectively make sense of this experience. For example, questions stay about what factors prevent professionals from seeking support, how the event affected their willingness to work with at-risk patients, and other concerns about how the event affected professionals.

Fourth Insight

The fourth insight that the review brings is the lack of theory that informs research in this area. Only two studies used any theory to get them to research or interpret the data. Joiner's theory of interpersonal suicide (IPTS). This theory postulates that suicidal desire arises from two psychological constructs: perceived burden (feeling like a burden to friends and loved ones) and inhibited belonging (low sense of belonging or social alienation). The result of repeated exposure to such events for suicide, through the process of repeatedly experiencing painful events such as being suicidal in the workplace, is the loss of the instinctive fear of death, or what is often described as the survival instinct. According to IPTS, both direct and indirect exposure can increase suicidal ability. The two papers listed in our review used the IPTS theoretical framework using the Acquired Suicidal Capacity Scale (ACSS) and the Interpersonal Needs Questionnaire (INQ) to access the constructs of the theory that compare it. The Suicidal Behavior Questionnaire Revised SBQ-R showed that suicide measures such as IPTS were not tested between mental health professionals' exposure to suicide. Despite using IPTS-derived measures, no studies have compared the suicidal exposure theory assumption as a possible cause of suicide. Theoretically informed research that focuses on understanding, not just explanation, is needed to advance our understanding of the context and risk of exposure to workplace suicide. This, in turn, will help inform the development of targeted evidence-based health promotion interventions in these professions.

Our review points to the high effects of suicidal exposure and implications for professionals' mental health and well-being. Like anxiety, these outcomes are associated with suicide risk. Due to the lack of research among paramedics and ambulance personnel, we cannot draw conclusions about the effects of exposure to suicide among these professionals. In addition, exposure to suicide appears to be associated with suicide risk among first responders and should be the focus of the suicide prevention protocol.

Strengths and Limitations

This scoping review has several strengths. First, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first review to examine the effects of suicidal exposure in the context of occupational exposure. He was also the first to review the literature on the effects of suicide exposure on first responders. Second, our review included a systematic and reproducible search for all major databases. Third, the articles included in our review were evaluated for quality, allowing us to find the strengths and weaknesses of the research and reporting. A fourth limitation found in the literature is the lack of definition of the relationship between healthcare professionals and the patient who died by suicide (eg, case manager, psychotherapist, or prescriber). Such improvement in data collection may explain how the relationship with the patient can affect professionals and personal responses.

Like any review, there are some limitations. Only peer-reviewed studies published in English in the past ten years were eligible for inclusion. Relevant earlier studies, non-English studies, or gray literature are likely to supply more information.

Scientific Literature

The scientific literature has focused on the study of exposure to suicide among different health professionals, but less attention has been paid to first responders, despite some limited, mainly quantitative research. Our review highlights some of its effects on exposure to suicide and how this may contribute to the negative mental health outcomes associated with an increased risk of suicide. The lack of research among first responders means that we are unable to draw any conclusions about the effects of suicidal exposure and suicidal risk exposure in these groups, this is especially true for paramedics. More research is needed on this phenomenon, particularly among police, firefighters, and ambulance workers/medical workers, given that going to a suicide scene can increase related outcomes. Further, more in-depth research into the effects of suicide exposure among first responders is necessary to understand how exposure to suicide through work affects the individual.[\[36\]](#)

More than 40 years ago, three psychologists came up with the eccentric, somewhat seductive headline "Lottery Winners and Accident Victims: Is Happiness Relative?" published a study entitled "Even if you don't think you know what you're writing, there's a good chance you will."

Operation is simple. As the title suggests, the authors surveyed a control group, hoping to compare their happiness levels with lottery winners and accident victims. But what the authors found violated common intuition. Victims rated themselves above average in terms of happiness, although they were less happy than controls, and their accidents had most recently resulted in either paraplegia or quadriplegia. If anything, the warps, and wefts of their daily lives were a bit older. Talking to friends, hearing jokes, having breakfast, all these simple pleasures were now less satisfying than before.

So, it was logical for Brickman to do such research. It was idiosyncratic, humanistic, and above all relevant: Does money satisfy us? Do irreparable damages in the body cause irreversible damages in the soul? Can we easily adapt to anything?

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In the end, what do we need to carry us?

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Shortly after publishing this work, Brickman went from Northwestern to the University of Michigan, where he became director of the oldest and most famous branch of the Institute for Social Research. It was a prestigious concert, an honor often given to academics at the peak of their careers. Paige, a retired professor of sociology at the University of Michigan, told me she thought Brickman would one day be appointed to the National Academy of Sciences.

"I almost had to imagine a different person to imagine what it was that drove him to do this," said Vita Carulli Rabinowitz, one of his former graduate students .

Most suicides are brutal mysteries, the "private and inexpressible" pain of the deceased, as Kay Redfield Jamison put it in his 1999 masterpiece "The Night Is Falling: Understanding Suicide." However, Brickman wrote more than 50 book chapters and academic articles in his short life, as well as a book published posthumously. So if Brickman was suffering from an underlying condition, as Rabinowitz argues, there was obviously too much hiding.[37]

Predicting precisely who will die by suicide has long eluded mental health professionals. There are no refined algorithms for this. Matthew K. Nock, professor of psychology at Harvard and the nation's leading scientist on suicide, conducted a famous study in 2010 that showed that clinicians in a major city psychiatric emergency room were no better at guessing who a coin flip after is leaving their care. would try suicide.

We know what factors make suicide more likely. Brickman checked almost every box. Recently separated. Two earlier suicide attempts. And the period when a person is at highest risk of dying by suicide is at once after leaving a psychiatric institution.

But the most common feature among people who die by suicide are symptoms of mental illness. Nock says they are present in 95 percent of all suicides, at least in

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the days or weeks before the event. And in Brickman's case, they were there much longer than that.

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Those who tried suicide reported higher Median scores for all three risk factor measures. Those who tried suicide reported significantly lower Median scores for all three measures of protective factor compared with those who did not try suicide. The results show that the group that tried suicide had a higher risk of suicide than the group that did not try suicide.

Those who tried suicide continued to report higher risk factor scores and lower protective factor scores, suggesting that they may continue to be more likely to try suicide. Key protective factors should be found for everyone to ensure proper clinical interventions to reduce the risk of retrying.

Peer Review Reports

Suicide has become a major public health problem with 800,000 deaths per year. The World Health Organization estimates that there are approximately 25 cases of suicide attempts for every suicide death. This modest estimate of 25 attempted suicides for every suicide death gives us an estimate that 20 million people try suicide annually.

The estimated suicide rate for 2015 in China is about 8/100,000 population. Based on an estimated population of 1.4 billion, this equates to at least 112,000 people per year. For every suicide death, about 135 other people experience significant adverse effects. This serves the roughly 15 million people in China who are adversely affected by suicide each year.

It is important for those who have tried suicide to understand and prevent future attempts. Past suicide attempts have been documented as one of the highest risk factors for another suicide attempt, with up to 20% of those trying re-attempts after the index attempt. There is also a need to better understand the risk factors and protective factors associated with suicide attempts. Risk factors are events or situations that are positively associated with suicidal behavior. A meta-analysis by Ribeiro and colleagues showed that individuals with hopelessness and depression had a weighted mean odds ratio of 1.63 (95% CI 1.55–1.72) to try suicide. Mood has also been found to prove diagnostic accuracy for sign of earlier and recent suicide attempts among undergraduates. Protective factors are important to minimize the temptation to engage in suicidal behavior. A meta-analysis of longitudinal studies by Soto-Sanz et al found that youth with lower self-esteem were up to twice as likely to try suicide in the future. Adolescents who reported lower social support from their parents, peers, and school were more likely to have a history of suicide attempts. Rodriguez and colleagues found that those who did not try self-harm and had a significantly higher life purpose compared to patients who tried suicide.

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Amid the downward trend in suicide rates in China over the past 20 years, an increase in suicide deaths among young adults has been reported. Analysis of risk, protective, and developmental factors that lead to suicidal attempts can improve

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our understanding of suicidal behaviors. For example, focusing on the life events of adolescents and young adults, as well as college-aged students (i.e., 18- to 24-year-olds in China) can be instrumental in increasing our understanding of factors associated with suicidal behavior. As individuals at this stage are just entering adulthood, they can offer valuable information that can help prevent further suicide attempts. In addition to the economic costs for this age group, the cost to families and society is also high. Therefore, it is important to evaluate how young people with a history of suicide attempt function psychologically, to better understand the causes of suicide attempts and to develop suicide prevention strategies.

Therefore, the main purpose of this study is to examine whether there is a difference in risk (depression, hopelessness, and mental pain) and psychiatric problems between individuals who attempt suicide and those who do not.[38]

A total of 11,806 students from seven provinces in China were recruited as potential participants. One university was selected by convenience sampling from each of the provinces of Ningxia, Shandong, Shanghai, Jilin, Qinghai, Xinjiang, and Shaanxi. Potential participants had to be between the ages of 18 and 22 to be eligible to take part in this study. Respondents were excluded where the responses were unreasonable, i.e., out of scope, not all elements of the R were complete, and/or (3) missing key demographic information such as gender.

Of the sample, 237 met the criteria for inclusion in the "Suicide Attempted" group. From the remaining 11,569 responses, a simple random sample of 1185 control cases (classified as the "non-Suicide" group) was drawn using the randomnumber generators function in SPSS. A control/case ratio of 5:1 was applied as it was associated with the lowest bias and higher sensitivity. Responses to an item in the Suicidal Behaviors Questionnaire-Revised were used to select study participants.

Precautions and Procedures

The Revised Suicidal Behaviors Questionnaire (SBQ-R) was developed for colleagues to assess various parameters of suicidal behavior, including past attempts, frequency of suicidal ideation, and probability of future attempts. They also suggested using (history of attempt) scores or SBQ-R total scores to develop subgroups of individuals with a history of suicide attempt/attempt and never tried suicide:

Suicide Attempt Group.

Participants who approved the response choice I tried to kill myself but did not want to die or I tried to kill myself and really hoped to die were assigned to the Suicide Attempt group.

Group Without Suicide Attempts.

Participants who approved the answer choice either never or only as a short transitional thought were considered the Non-Suicide Attempt group.

Despair

Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) was used to measure negative attitudes towards the future. The response options of this 20-item scale were converted from yes/no to a 5-point Likert-type scale and ranged from 1 to 5. (Strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). The Chinese version of the BHS was found to have acceptable reliability and validity among Chinese university students.

Depression (DASS-42)

The Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS), which consists of 42 items, is designed to evaluate negative moods according to three subscales, especially depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms. There are 7 items per subscale and are graded on a 4-point scale ranging from 0 to 3, and the DASS Lower scores at -42 mean better mental health. The instrument is widely used in China for various psychosocial work such as Cheng et al.

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The Psychic Pain Scale consists of 13 items reflecting mental pain (i.e., mental pain), scored from 1 to 5, with higher scores showing a higher level of agreement. Psychache Scale scores have acceptable psychometric properties. Coefficient- α estimates of 0.94 were found when completed by Chinese university students.

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Social support

The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) has 12 items rated on a 7-point Likert-type response scale that measures social support. The total score ranges from 12 to 84, and higher scores on this scale show greater social support. The scale consists of three sources of social support, including family members, friends, or significant others (or special person). The Median score was 63 ± 0.48 and the Median score was 1 (min = 0, max = 1), while the Mean score of those who did not try suicide was 0.11 ± 0.31 and the Median score was 0 (0.1). The difference was significant ($U = 214,248.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is medium (0.72).

Risk factors for suicide

The attempting group also scored significantly ($p > 0.001$) higher on each measure of risk factor for suicide, namely hopelessness, mental pain, and depression, compared with the non-intervention group.

Despair

The Mean score of those who tried suicide was 55.0 ± 8.4 and the Median score was 56 (min = 32, max = 79), while the Mean score of those who did not try suicide was 50.4 ± 9.4 and a Median score of 50 (27, 91). ($U = 170,489.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is small (0.28).

Self-respect

For self-esteem, the mean score of the group who tried suicide was 25.4 ± 3.9 and Median score of 25 (min = 12, max = 37), Mean score of those who did not try suicide is 27.3. He had a 3.7 and a Median score . 27 (14, 37). The difference was significant ($U = 97,582.00$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d is small (0.40).

Purpose in Life

Mean score of the group who tried suicide in the measurement for life purpose was 18.2 ± 5.1 and Median score of 19 (min = 4, max= 28), Mean score of those who did not try suicide is 20.4 ± 4.6 and the Median score is 21 (4. 28). The difference was significant ($U = 97,632.50$, $p < 0.001$). The effect size using Cohen's d was small (0.40).

Suicide Attempt Risk

The binary logistic regression model for the factors predicting suicide attempt was significant, $\chi^2(8) = 224.65$, $p < 0.001$, explaining 11.4% of the variance in suicide attempt (Nagelkerke R²) and correctly classifying 98% of the cases. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test require $p > 0.05$ for a good fit. In the current analysis, $p = 0.252$ and therefore the model was a good fit for the data. Regression results showed that those who were more depressed had the highest risk of trying suicide (OR 1.123, 95% CI: 1.076, 1.173, $p < 0.001$); they also had a high score for mental pain (OR 1.045, 95% CI: 1.028, 1.063, $p < 0.001$). Younger age was most protective against suicide attempts (OR 0.870, 95% CI: 0.783, 0.967, $p < 0.001$) (See Table 4).

These findings show that those who have tried suicide are more likely to have thoughts of the past year, lifetime threat, and future attempt compared to their peers who have not tried suicide before. Suicide attempters also reported higher risk factors such as more hopelessness, mental pain, and depression, and significantly lower protective factors (social support, self-esteem, and life purpose) in univariate analyses. However, in the multiple regression model, only mental pain and depression remained important risk factors, while social support and early age were protective factors. Hopelessness had become an important protective factor, but the results may not be normal as the effect sizes in the t-test and multivariate analyzes are small and negligible.

Consequences of Mental Pain, Depression, and Social Support as Predictors of Suicide Attempts

It is consistent with a number of past studies conducted inside and outside of China. The results show that the group that tried suicide had a higher risk of suicide compared to the group that did not try suicide.

From the study, suicidal attempters appear to report psychological characteristics like a potential suicide attempt, with high suicide risk and high scores on risk factors and low scores on protective factors. An elevated risk of suicide may

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increase the risk of trying suicide again. Therefore, there is a need to formulate intervention strategies and programs for suicide attempters based on an established and agreed concept of suicide rescue/rehabilitation. This is ideally

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more than suicide .It should include an understanding of what “being saved ” means for everyone. Basic protective factors should be decided for each individual and should be studied by mental health professionals to be protective. Such individuals can benefit significantly from psychotherapy or medication. Specifically, cognitive behavioral therapy with the goals of curing depression and negative self-image while setting up hope and purpose in life can alleviate suicidal behaviors. Also, universities can implement universal suicide prevention efforts, such as gatekeeper training, which can indirectly generate social support for college students struggling with suicidal thoughts.

Cross-sectional research design does not allow us to infer causality. Given the breadth, diversity, and large population of a country like China, one cannot generalize to other universities, provinces, rural areas, other age groups, or other segments of society without further research. Context and time-lapse from earlier suicide attempts, participation in any rehabilitation program, whether participants tried suicide only once or more than once are unknown.

Future research may focus on ways and means of reducing risk factors and increasing protective factors for surviving suicide attempt, especially when following their cases after hospital discharge. Universities can also incorporate this important suicide prevention risk management program into their programs. More research is needed on attitudes towards suicide among adolescents, with more initiatives for diversity and inclusion. It may be worth exploring as a future avenue for increased awareness and further research in this area for healthcare professionals to better define suicide. A proper rehabilitation and monitoring program may be necessary to reduce long-term risk factors and nurture protective factors.

This study shows that undergraduate students who reported an earlier suicide attempt continued to have higher risk factor scores and lower protective factor scores. The results raise concern that these at-risk students may continue to be more likely to try suicide. Therefore, proper clinical interventions should be found to reduce the risk of retrying and improve their overall psychological health.

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Suicide is the act of deliberately causing one's own death. Mental disorders (including depression, bipolar disorder, autism spectrum disorders, schizophrenia,

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personality disorders, anxiety disorders), nihilistic beliefs, physical disorders (such as chronic fatigue syndrome), and substance use disorders (including alcohol use disorder and alcohol use and withdrawal benzodiazepines) are risk factors.[39]

The most common method of suicide differs between countries and is partly related to the availability of effective means. Common suicide methods include hanging, pesticide poisoning, and firearms. Suicide resulted in 828,000 global deaths in 2015, an increase from 712,000 deaths in 1990, making suicide the 10th leading cause of death worldwide.

About 1.5% of all deaths worldwide are suicides. Each year this is about 12 per 100,000 people. Completed suicide rates are generally higher among men than women, ranging from 1.5 times in developing countries to 3.5 times in developed countries. Suicide is usually most common among those over the age of 70; however, in some countries those aged 15 to 30 are at the highest risk in Europe had the highest suicide rates by region in 2015. It is estimated that there are between 10 and 20 million non-fatal suicide tries each year. Non-fatal suicide attempts can result in injury and long-term disability. In the western world, enterprises are mostly seen among young people and women.

Views About Suicide

Views about suicide have been influenced by broad existential themes such as religion, honor, and the meaning of life. Abrahamic religions traditionally consider suicide a crime against God because of belief in the sanctity of life. During the samurai era in Japan, seppuku, a form of suicide known as hara-kiri, was revered as compensation for failure or a form of protest. Sati, a practice banned by the British, expected an Indian widow to kill herself at her husband's funeral pyre, either willingly or under pressure from family and society. Suicide and attempted suicide, while previously illegal, are no longer so in most Western countries. It stays a criminal offense in more countries. In the 20th and 21st centuries, suicide has rarely been used as a form of protest, and kamikaze and suicide bombs have been used as a military or terrorist tactic. Suicide is often viewed as a major disaster for families, relatives, and other supporters nearby, and is viewed negatively almost everywhere in the world.

Suicide Terminology

Suicide, which comes from the Latin word for suicide, is "the act of ending one's own life". Suicide attempt or non-fatal suicidal behavior is self-harm that does not result in death, at least with the desire to end a person's life. Aided suicide is when one person helps another person indirectly commit their own death by offering advice or a way to a conclusion. This contrasts with euthanasia, where another person takes a more active role in causing a person's death. Suicidal thoughts are thoughts of ending one's life but not making an active effort to do so. It may or may not include precise planning or intent. In a murder-suicide (or murder-suicide) individual also aims to take the lives of others. A particular example of this is extended suicide, in which murder is motivated by viewing the murdered persons as an extension of their selves. Suicide due to feeling that one is not part of society is known as egoistic suicide.

In 2011, Canada's Center for Suicide Prevention processed the regular verb unrealism for the act of suicide in scientific research. Some advocacy groups recommend using the terms completed suicide, committed suicide, died by suicide, or killed himself instead of committing suicide. The Associated Press Stylebook recommends avoiding "attempted suicide" except for direct quotes from authorities. Opponents of commitment argue that suicide implies guilt, sin, or morally wrong.

Risk factors

Factors that influence suicide risk include mental disorders, drug use, psychological conditions, cultural, familial, and social situations, genetics, experiences of trauma or loss, and nihilism. Mental disorders and substance abuse often coexist. Other risk factors include an earlier suicide attempt, the availability of a means to take someone's life, a family history of suicide, or a traumatic brain injury. For example, suicide rates were found to be higher in households with firearms than those without weapons.

Socio-economic problems such as unemployment, poverty, homelessness, and discrimination can trigger suicidal thoughts. Suicide may be rarer in societies with high social cohesion and moral objections to suicide. About 15-40% of people

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leave a suicide note. War veterans have a higher risk of suicide, in part because of higher rates of mental illness such as post-traumatic stress disorder and war-

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related physical health issues. Genetics appear to handle 38% to 55% of suicidal behaviors. Suicides can also occur as a local cluster of cases.[40]

Mental Illness

Mental illness is present in 27% to more than 90% at the time of suicide. The lifetime risk of completed suicide for those hospitalized for suicidal behavior is 8.6%. Comparatively, people who are hospitalized for mood disorders in non-suicidal individuals have a 4% lifetime risk of suicide. Half of all people who die by suicide may have major depressive disorder; Having this or one of the mood disorders such as bipolar disorder increases the risk of suicide by 20 times. Other conditions affected include schizophrenia (14%), personality disorders (8%), obsessive-compulsive disorder, and post-traumatic stress disorder. Those with autism spectrum disorder also try suicide more often and think about it.[41]

Among about 80% of completed suicides, the individual saw a doctor in the year before their death, 45% in the previous month. Approximately 25-40% of those who completed suicide had been in contact with mental health services in the previous year. Antidepressants of the SSRI class appear to increase the frequency of suicide among children but not change the risk among adults. Unwillingness to seek help for mental health problems also increases the risk.

Earlier Attempts and Self-Harm

History of suicide attempt is the most correct predictor of completed suicide. About 20% of suicides have made an earlier attempt, and 1% of those who try suicide complete it within one year, and more than 5% die by suicide within 10 years. Acts of self-harming are not usually suicide attempts, and most self-harming people are not at substantial risk of suicide. However, some self-harms end their lives by suicide, and the risk of self-harm and suicide may overlap.

Psychosocial Factors

A number of psychological factors increase the risk of suicide: hopelessness, a lack of enjoyment of life, depression, anxiety, agitation, rigid thinking, rumination, thought suppression, and poor coping skills are the first to be involved. A poor ability to solve problems, loss of abilities, and poor impulse control also play a role. The feeling of being a burden to others is important in older adults. Those who have never been married are also at greater risk. Recent life stressors, such as the loss of a family member or friend or job loss, may be a contributing factor.

Certain personality factors, particularly prominent levels of neuroticism and introversion, have been associated with suicide. On the one hand, optimism has been shown to have a protective effect. Other psychological risk factors include having several reasons to live and feeling trapped in a stressful situation. Changes in the stress response system in the brain can change in suicidal situations.[\[42\]](#)

Social isolation and lack of social support have been associated with an increased risk of suicide. Poverty is also a factor, with relative poverty increasing the risk of suicide compared to those around a person. More than 200,000 farmers have died by suicide in India since 1997, in part due to debt problems. In China, rural areas are three times more likely to commit suicide than urban areas, partly due to financial difficulties in this part of the country.

While being religious can reduce a person's risk of suicide, beliefs that suicide is noble can increase it. This has been associated with the negative attitude many religions have towards suicide and the greater commitment that religion can impart. Among religious people, Muslims seem to have lower suicide rates; but the data to support this is not strong. There is no difference in suicide attempt rates. Rates of young women in the Middle East may be higher.

Substance Use

Alcoholism how to poverty, crime and suicide could lead to the end showing "The Drunkard's Progress" 'For example, substance use is the second most common risk factor for suicide after major depression and bipolar disorder. Both chronic substance abuse and acute intoxication are related. The risk is even greater when combined with personal grief, such as bereavement. Substance use is also associated with mental health disorders.

Most people are under the influence of sedative-hypnotic drugs (such as alcohol or benzodiazepines) when they die by suicide, with alcoholism present in 15% to 61% of cases. Use of prescription benzodiazepines is associated with an increased rate of suicide attempts and completed suicides. The suicidal effects of benzodiazepines are suspected to be due to a psychiatric disorder caused by side effects such as disinhibition or withdrawal symptoms. Countries with higher rates of alcohol use and greater bar density generally have higher suicide rates. Approximately 2.2-3.4% of those treated for alcoholism at some point in their lives die by suicide. Alcoholics who try suicide are usually male, elderly, and have tried suicide in the past. Between 3% and 35% of deaths among heroin users are due to suicide (approximately fourteen times more than nonusers).[97] Neurological and psychological disorders may contribute to an increased risk of suicide in adolescents who abuse alcohol.

Cocaine and methamphetamine abuse has a high association with suicide in cocaine users, the risk is greatest in the withdrawal phase. Inhalant users are also at significant risk, and around 20% attempt suicide at some point, and more than 65% consider this.[50] Smoking is associated with an increased risk of suicide. There is little evidence as to why this relationship exists; however, it has been assumed that those who are prone to smoking are also suicidal, that smoking causes health problems and therefore causes people to want to end their lives, and that smoking affects brain chemistry and is suicidal. But cannabis does not appear to increase risk independently.

Medical Conditions

There is an association between suicidal tendencies and physical health problems such as chronic pain, traumatic brain injury, cancer, chronic fatigue syndrome, kidney failure (requiring hemodialysis), HIV, and systemic lupus erythematosus. A cancer diagnosis approximately doubles the incidence of later suicides. The increased prevalence of suicide continued after adjustment for depressive illness and excessive alcohol use. This frequency was particularly high in people with multiple medical conditions. In Japan, health problems are listed as the primary reason for suicide.[\[43\]](#)

It is subject to referral with symptoms like mood disorders such as hypothyroidism, Alzheimer's, brain tumors, systemic lupus erythematosus, and side effects of a number of drugs (such as beta-blockers and steroids).

Media

The media, including the Internet, play a significant role. With high-volume, prominent, repetitive coverage that glorifies or romanticizes suicide, certain depictions of suicide can increase the occurrence of suicide. This method of suicide can be imitated in vulnerable individuals when detailed explanations of how to kill oneself in a certain way are shown. This phenomenon has been seen in several cases after media coverage. One of the effective ways to reduce the negative impact of media portrayals of suicide news is to train journalists on how to report news in a way that reduces the likelihood of fake news and encourages those at risk to seek help. The risk of suicide can be reduced when journalists follow certain reporting rules. But getting a share of the media industry can be difficult, especially eventually.

This trigger of suicidal contagion or copycat suicide is known as the "Werther effect", named after the protagonist in Goethe's *The Sorrows of Young Werther*, who killed himself and was later emulated by many of the book's fans. This risk is greater in adolescents who may romanticize death. It seems that while the news media has a major influence, the influence of the entertainment media is ambiguous. It is unclear whether searching for information about suicide on the Internet is associated with suicide risk. The opposite of the Werther effect is the proposed "Papageno effect", where the extent of effective coping mechanisms may have a protective effect. The term is based on a character in Mozart's opera *The Magic Flute* - fearing losing someone he loved, he had planned to kill himself until his friends helped him out. As a result, fictional depictions of suicide showing alternative outcomes or negative outcomes can have a preventative effect, for example, fiction can normalize mental health problems and encourage help-seeking.

Other Factors

Trauma is a risk factor for suicide in both children and adults. Some may take their own lives to escape bullying or prejudice. A history of childhood sexual abuse and time spent in a foster family are also risk factors. Sexual abuse is believed to contribute to about 20% of the overall risk. Significant distress early in life has a negative impact on problem-solving skills and memory, both of which tend to be suicidal.

Gambling is associated with increased suicidal thoughts and attempts compared to the general population. Between 12 and 24% of pathological gamblers try suicide. The rate of suicide among spouses is three times higher than in the general population. Other factors that increase risk in problem gamblers include concomitant mental illness, alcohol, and drug use.

Genetics can affect completed suicide rates. A family history of suicide, especially in the mother, affects children more than adolescents or adults. Adoption studies have shown that this is the case for biological relatives, but not for adopted relatives. This cuts the possibility of familial risk factors from mimicry. When mental disorders are considered, the estimated heritability is 36% for suicidal ideation and 17% for suicide attempt. One evolutionary explanation for suicide is that it can improve inclusive fitness. This can happen if the person who died by suicide did not have any more children and survived and inherited resources from relatives. One objection is that the deaths of healthy adolescents probably do not increase inclusive fitness. Adapting to a vastly different ancestral environment may be incompatible in the current environment.

Infection by the parasite *Toxoplasma gondii*, more commonly known as toxoplasmosis, has been associated with an increased risk of suicide. One explanation states that this is due to altered neurotransmitter activity depending on the immunological response.^[44]

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Rational suicide is the justified ending of one's own life. But some never see suicide as something rational.

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Euthanasia and assisted suicide are practices accepted among those with mediocre quality of life together in many countries. Hope is the possibility of getting better. It is supported by legal arguments for the right to die.

The act of taking one's own life for the benefit of others is known as altruistic suicide. An example of this is an elder who takes his own life to leave more food for the youth in the community. In some Inuit cultures, suicide was viewed as an act of respect, courage, or wisdom.

A suicide attack is a political or religious act of violence against others that the attacker understands will result in his or her death. Some suicide bombers are driven by the desire to become a martyr or by religious motivation. Kamikaze missions were performed as a mission to a higher cause or moral obligation. Murder-suicide is an act of murder followed by the suicide of the person who committed it within a week.

mass suicides

Mass suicides are often carried out under social pressure where members give up autonomy to a leader. Mass suicides can happen with at least two people, often referred to as a suicide pact. In extenuating situations where continuing to live is unbearable, some people use suicide as an escape route. Some prisoners in Nazi concentration camps are known to have killed themselves by deliberately touching electrified fences during the Holocaust.

Preferred Suicide Methods

The leading method of suicide differs between countries. Among the leading methods in different regions are hanging, pesticide poisoning and firearms. These differences are believed to be due in part to the availability of different methods. A review of 56 countries found that in most countries hanging was the most common method, accounting for 53% of male suicides and 39% of female suicides.

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It is estimated that 30% of suicides worldwide are due to pesticide poisoning, most of which occur in developing countries. Use of this method varies markedly, from

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4% in Europe to more than 50% in the Pacific region. It is also common in Latin America due to its ease of access among the farming population. In many countries, drug overdose handles around 60% of suicides among women and 30% among men. Many are unplanned and occur during a period of acute indecision. Mortality varies by method: firearms 80-90%, drowning 65-80%, hanging 60-85%, jumping 35-60%, coal burning 40-50%, pesticides 60-75%, and drug overdose 1.5- 4.0%. The most common suicide attempt methods differ from the most common completion methods; In the developed world, up to 85% of attempts are made through drug overdoses.

Pesticide consumption is the most common method in China. In Japan, self-piercing, known as seppuku (hara-kiri), still occurs; but the most common ones are hanging and jumping. Jumping to death is common in both Hong Kong and Singapore at 50% and 80% respectively. In Switzerland, firearms are the most common method of suicide among young men, but this method has relatively declined as guns have become less common. In the United States, 50% of suicides involve the use of firearms, and this method is slightly more common in men (56%) than in women (31%). The next most common cause was hanging in men (28%) and self-poisoning in women (31%). Together, hanging and poisoning accounted for about 42% of U.S. suicides (as of 2017).

pathophysiology

There is no known unifying pathophysiology underlying suicide. However, it is believed to result from the interaction of behavioral, socio-economic, and psychological factors.

Low levels of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) are both directly associated with suicide[148] and indirectly through its role in major depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, schizophrenia, and obsessive-compulsive disorder. Post-mortem studies have found decreased levels of BDNF in the hippocampus and prefrontal cortex in those with and without psychiatric disorders. Serotonin, a brain neurotransmitter, is believed to be low in those who die by suicide. This is partly based on evidence that the levels of 5-HT_{2A} receptors found after death are increased. Other evidence includes reduced levels of the degradation product of serotonin, 5-hydroxyindolacetic acid, in the cerebrospinal fluid.[153] However, direct evidence is difficult to gather. Epigenetics, the study of changes in genetic expression in response to environmental factors that do not alter the underlying DNA, is also believed to play a role in deciding suicidal risk.

Prevention

Suicide prevention is a term used for collective efforts to reduce the incidence of suicide through preventive measures. Protective factors for suicide include access to support and treatment. About 60% of people with suicidal thoughts do not seek help. Reasons for not doing this include low perceived need and willingness to deal with the problem alone. Despite these high rates, few established treatments for suicidal behavior exist.

Reducing access to certain methods, such as firearms or toxins such as opioids and pesticides, can reduce the risk of suicide with this method. This may be partly because suicide is often an impulsive decision, and 70% of near-death suicide attempts are made after less than an hour of thought. To be successful. Other measures include reducing access to coal (for burning) and adding barriers to bridges and subway platforms. Treatment for drug and alcohol abuse, depression, and those who have tried suicide in the past can also be effective. Some have suggested reducing access to alcohol as a preventative strategy (for example, reducing the number of bars).

In young adults who have recently contemplated suicide, cognitive behavioral therapy appears to improve outcomes. School-based programs that increase mental health literacy and train staff have shown mixed results on suicide rates. Thanks to its ability to reduce poverty, economic development can reduce suicide rates. Efforts to increase social connection can be effective, especially in older men. Repeated follow-ups can be prevented in people who try suicide. While crisis helplines are common, there is little evidence to support or refute their effectiveness. Preventing childhood trauma supplies an opportunity to prevent suicide. World Suicide Prevention Day is celebrated on 10 September each year with the support of the International Suicide Prevention Association and the World Health Organization.

Scanning

There is little data on the effects of screening the general population on the final suicide rate. Screening those injured by self-harm in emergency departments has been shown to help find suicidal ideation and suicidal intention. Psychometric tests such as the Beck Depression Inventory or the Geriatric Depression Scale are used for the elderly. Because of the high proportion of people who test positive with these tools that are not at risk of suicide, there are concerns that screening could significantly increase the use of mental health care resources. However, it is recommended to evaluate those at substantial risk. Asking about suicide does not seem to increase the risk.

Mental Illness

For those with mental health problems, a range of treatments can reduce the risk of suicide. Those who are actively suicidal can be admitted to psychiatric care voluntarily or unwillingly. Items that could be used to self-harm are typically removed. Some clinicians have patients sign suicide prevention contracts, which they agree will not harm themselves if they are released. However, the evidence does not support a significant effect of this practice. If a person is at insignificant risk, outpatient mental health treatment may be arranged. In those with borderline personality disorder who are chronically suicidal, short-term hospitalization was not found to be more effective in the community for improving outcomes.

There is tentative evidence that psychotherapy, particularly dialectical behavior therapy, reduces suicide in adolescents and those with borderline personality disorder. It may also be useful in reducing suicide attempts in adults at substantial risk. But the evidence did not find a reduction in completed suicides.

There is debate about the benefit-harm relationship of antidepressants. In teenagers, certain antidepressants, such as SSRIs, appear to increase the risk of suicide from 25 per 1000 to 40 per 1000. But they can reduce the risk in older people. Lithium appears to be effective in reducing the risk in those with bipolar disorder and major depression to nearly the same as in the general population. Clozapine may reduce suicidal thoughts in some people with schizophrenia. Ketamine, a dissociative anesthetic, appears to reduce the rate of suicidal ideation. In the United States, healthcare professionals are legally required to take reasonable steps to try to prevent suicide.

About 0.5% to 1.4% of people die by suicide, the death rate being 11.6 per 100,000 people per year. Suicide resulted in 842,000 deaths in 2013, down from 712,000 deaths in 1990. From the 1960s to 2012, suicide rates increased by 60%, and these increases were seen primarily in developing countries. Globally, as of 2008/2009, suicide is the tenth leading cause of death. For every suicide that results in death, there are 10 to 40 suicide attempts.

Suicide rates vary considerably between countries and over time. The percentage of deaths in 2008 were: Africa 0.5%, South-East Asia 1.9%, America 1.2%, and Europe 1.4%. Rates per 100,000 inhabitants: Australia 8.6, Canada 11.1, China 12.7, India 23.2, United Kingdom 7.6, United States 11.4, and South Korea 28.9. It was ranked as the 10th leading cause of death in the United States in 2016, with approximately 45,000 cases that year. Rates have increased over the last few years in the United States, with the highest value in 2017 (latest data). In the United States, about 650,000 people go to emergency rooms each year for a suicide attempt. The proportion among men in their 50s in the United States nearly halved between 1999 and 2010. Greenland, Lithuania, Japan, and Hungary have the highest suicide rates. About 75% of suicides occur in developing countries. The countries with the highest absolute number of suicides are China and India, which account for more than half of the total, partly because of their large populations. Suicide is the 5th leading cause of death in China.

Globally, as of 2012, death by suicide is approximately 1.8 times more common in men than in women. In the Western world, men die by suicide three to four times more often than women. This difference is even more pronounced in people over the age of 65, with men ten times more likely to die from suicide than women. Suicide attempts and self-harm are two to four times more common among women. The researchers attributed the gender gap between attempted suicide and completed suicide to men using more lethal means to end their lives. However, separating intentional suicide attempts from non-suicidal self-harm is not currently done when collecting statistics at the national level in places like the United States.

China has one of the highest female suicide rates in the world and is the only country where it is higher than that of men (0.9 rate). Suicide rates in the eastern Mediterranean are nearly equivalent among men and women. The highest female suicide rate, at 22 per 100,000, is found in South Korea, with rates generally higher in Southeast Asia and the Western Pacific.

A number of studies have found an increased risk of suicide among lesbian, gay,

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bisexual, and transgender people. Among transgender people, suicide attempt rates are approximately 40% compared to 5% in the general population. This is believed to be partly due to social stigma.

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Suicide Rates by Age

In many countries, the suicide rate is highest in the middle-aged or elderly. But the absolute number of suicides is greatest among those aged 15-29, due to the number of people in this age group. Worldwide, the average age of suicide for both men and women are between 30 and 49. This means that half of those who die by suicide are about 40 years old or younger, and half are older. Suicide is rare in children but increases during the transition to puberty.

In the United States, the suicide death rate is highest in white men older than 80, although younger people try suicide more often. It is the second most common cause of death in adolescents and second only to accidental death in young men. It is the cause of about 30% of deaths in young men in the developed world. Rates in developing countries are similar, but account for a smaller proportion of overall deaths due to higher death rates from other types of traumata. In Southeast Asia, unlike other parts of the world, deaths from suicide occur at a higher rate in younger women than in older women.

Historical Data on Suicide

While suicide was initially allowed in ancient Rome, it was later considered a crime against the state due to its economic costs. While Aristotle condemned any form of suicide, Plato was undecided. Some causes of suicide in Rome include dying voluntarily in gladiatorial combat, feeling guilty about killing someone, mourning saving someone else's life, embarrassment of being raped, and escaping excruciating situations such as physical pain. There is military defeat or criminal pursuit.

Suicide came to be seen as a sin in Christian Europe and was condemned as the work of Satan at the Council of Arles (452). In the Middle Ages, the Church had long debates about when the desire to be a martyr became suicidal, as with the martyrs of Córdoba. Despite these debates and occasional official resolutions, Catholic doctrine was not fully settled on suicide until the late 17th century. King of France XIV in 1670. A penal code enacted by Louis was extremely severe even then: The body of the deceased was pulled from the streets, face down, and then hung or thrown into a garbage heap. In addition, all the person's property was confiscated.

Attitudes towards suicide gradually began to change during the Renaissance. John Donne's work *Bia Thanatos* included one of the first modern defenses of suicide, bringing evidence from the behavior of Biblical figures such as Jesus, Samson, and Saul, and presenting reason and nature-based arguments to justify suicide in certain situations.

The secularization of society that began during the Enlightenment questioned traditional religious attitudes towards suicide (such as Christian views on suicide) and brought a more modern perspective to the issue. David Hume denied that suicide was a crime, as it did not affect anyone and potentially helped the individual. In his 1777 *Essays on Suicide and the Immorality of the Soul*, he rhetorically asked, "Why should I prolong a miserable existence because of some

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trivial advantage the public can take from me?" asked. Hume's analysis was criticized by the philosopher Philip. He described Reed as "uncharacteristically bad (for him)" because Hume took an unusually narrow sense of duty, and his

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conclusion was that suicide should not cause any harm to others—including not causing grief, guilt, or emotional pain to any surviving friend and family. – which is almost never the case. A change in public opinion can also be noticed; In 1786, The Times asked, "Is suicide an act of courage?" sparked a heated debate over his proposal.

By the 19th century, the act of suicide changed from being seen as caused by sin in Europe to an event caused by insanity. Although suicide remained illegal during this period, it increasingly became the target of satirical interpretations such as Gilbert and Sullivan's comic opera Mikado.

By 1879, English law had begun to distinguish between suicide and murder, but suicide still led to the confiscation of property. In 1882, the deceased was allowed to be buried in the light of day in England[213] and by the middle of the 20th century, suicide had become legal in most of the Western world. The term suicide first appeared shortly before 1700 to replace expressions of self-death, which in the West is often described as a form of self-death.

Suicide Legislation

Currently, no country in Europe considers suicide or attempted suicide as a crime. However, this was the case in most Western European countries from the Middle Ages to at least the 19th century. The Netherlands was the first country to legalize both doctor-assisted suicide and euthanasia, enacted in 2002, but both only allow doctors to aid and must follow a protocol prescribed by Dutch law. Failure to follow such a protocol is an offense punishable by law. Active euthanasia is illegal in Germany, and anyone found at the time of suicide can be prosecuted for not aiding in an emergency. Switzerland has taken steps to legalize assisted suicide for the chronically mentally ill. The supreme court in Lausanne, Switzerland, in a 2006 decision granted an unidentified individual with long-standing psychiatric problems the right to end his own life. England and Wales decriminalized suicide through the Suicide Act 1961 and the Republic of Ireland in 1993.

Suicide is not illegal in the United States, but it can be associated with penalties for those who try it. In Washington state, physician-assisted suicide is legal for people with terminal illness. In Oregon, people with terminal illness can request drugs to end their life. Canadians who have tried suicide may be barred from entering the United States. US law allows border guards to block access to people with mental illness, including those who have previously attempted suicide.

Suicide is not a crime in Australia. However, advising, inciting, or aiding and abetting another person who is trying to die by suicide is a crime, and the law expressly allows any person to use "force as reasonably necessary" to prevent another person from taking their own life. The Northern Territory of Australia briefly committed legal doctor-assisted suicide from 1996 to 1997.

Suicide used to be illegal in India and the surviving family could face legal challenges. The Indian government repealed this law in 2014. It stays a criminal offense in predominantly Muslim countries.

Religious Views

Most forms of Christianity, mainly St. Augustine and St. Based on the writings of influential Christian thinkers of the Middle Ages, such as Thomas Aquinas, he considers suicide to be sinful, but in the Byzantine Christian code of Justinian, for example, suicide was not considered a sin. In Catholic doctrine, the argument is based on the commandment "Thou shalt not kill" (made enforceable by Jesus in the Gospel of Matthew under the New Testament), as well as the idea that life is a gift from God. should not be rejected, and suicide goes against the "natural order" and thus interferes with God's overall plan for the world. However, it is believed that mental illness or fear of serious suffering reduces the responsibility of the person who committed the suicide.

Judaism focuses on the importance of valuing this life, and thus suicide is tantamount to denying God's goodness on earth. However, there are several accounts of Jews dying by suicide, either individually or in groups, under extreme circumstances where they had no choice but to be killed or forced to betray their religion (see, for example, the Jews and York Castle), and as a grim reminder, Jewish ritual "with the knife in the throat", there is even a prayer to "sanctify the Name of God" for the deceased (see Martyrdom). These actions received mixed reactions from Jewish authorities, viewed by some as examples of heroic martyrdom, while others pointing out that it was wrong to take their own lives in anticipation of martyrdom.

Islamic religious views are against suicide. The Qur'an forbids this by saying "do not kill or destroy yourself". It is said in the hadiths that individual suicide is haram and sinful. Stigma in Islamic countries is often associated with suicide.

In Hinduism, suicide is often despised and considered as sinful in contemporary Hindu society as killing another person. The Hindu Scriptures state that a person who dies by suicide will become part of the spirit world, wandering the world until he would otherwise die if he had not taken his own life. However, Hinduism recognizes the right to end a person's life through the practice of nonviolent death fasting, called Prayopavesa; but Prayopavesa is strictly limited to people who have

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no desire or ambition left and who have no responsibility left in this life. Jainism has a similar practice called Santhara. Self-immolation by Sati or widows is a rare and illegal practice in Hindu society.

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In the Ainu religion, it is believed that someone who dies by suicide is a ghost (tukap) that will haunt the living, achieving the satisfaction they have been excluded throughout life. In addition, a person who insults another and kills himself is jointly and severally liable for his death. According to Norbert Richard Adami, this ethic exists because solidarity within the community is far more important to Ainu culture than to the Western world.

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Suicide Philosophy

A number of questions arise in the philosophy of suicide, including what suicide is, whether suicide would be a rational choice, and whether suicide is morally permissible.[45]

Opponents of suicide include philosophers such as Augustine of Hippo, Thomas Aquinas,[242] Immanuel Kant, and arguably John Stuart Mill. to make autonomous decisions in the future. Others view suicide as a legitimate matter of personal choice. Proponents of this view argue that no one should be compelled to suffer against their will, especially from incurable conditions such as illness, mental illness, and old age, which are unlikely to heal. They reject the belief that suicide is always irrational, suggesting instead that it can be a practical last resort for those who have suffered great pain or trauma. A stronger stance would argue that people should be allowed to choose to die autonomously, regardless of whether they are suffering or not. Notable supporters of this school of thought include the Scottish empiricist David Hume and the American bioethicist Jacob Appel, who concede to suicide if it does not violate a duty or harm to God, other people, or himself.

Suicide Advocacy

In this painting by Alexandre-Gabriel Decamps, the pallet, the pistol, and the note on the floor show that the event has just happened; An artist took his own life. Suicide advocacy has appeared in many cultures and subcultures. During World War II, the Japanese military encouraged and glorified kamikaze attacks, which were suicide attacks against Allied naval ships by military aviators from the Empire of Japan during the closing stages of the Pacific Theater of World War II. Japanese society has been described as "suicide tolerant".

The Internet searches for information on suicidal relapse web pages that encourage, or ease suicide tries 10-30% of the time. There are some concerns that such sites may push the prone to the sidelines. Some people create suicide pacts online with pre-existing friends or people they've met recently in chat rooms or message boards. But the internet can also help prevent suicide by supplying a social group for isolated people.

Some highlights have become known for their prominent level of suicide attempts. These include China's Nanjing Yangtze River Bridge, San Francisco's Golden Gate Bridge, Japan's Aokigahara Forest, England's Beachy Head and Toronto's Bloor Street Viaduct[25]. As of 2018, the Golden Gate Bridge has killed more than 1,300 people by suicide by jumping since it was built in 1937. In many places where suicide is common, barriers have been built to prevent suicide; this includes the Luminous Veil in Toronto,[253] the Eiffel Tower in Paris, the West Gate Bridge in Melbourne, and the Empire State Building in New York City.

important cases

An example of mass suicide is the 1978 Jonestown mass murder/suicide, in which 909 members of the People's Temple, a new American religious movement led by Jim Jones, ended their lives by ingesting grape flavoring laced with cyanide and various prescription drugs.

In the final days of the Battle of Saipan in 1944, thousands of Japanese civilians committed suicide, some by jumping from the "Suicide Abyss" and "Banzai Abyss". The 1981 Irish hunger strikes led by Bobby Sands resulted in 10 deaths. The cause of death was recorded by the coroner as "hunger, self-imposed" rather than suicide; this was changed to simply "hunger" in the death certificates after the families of the deceased strikers protested. During the Second World War, it was found that Erwin Rommel foreshadowed the plot about Hitler's life on July 20; He was threatened with public trial, execution, and retaliation against his family if he did not take his own life.

Animal Suicide

Because suicide requires a deliberate attempt to die, some believe it cannot be said to occur in non-human animals. Suicidal behavior has been seen in *Salmonella*, which tries to defeat rival bacteria by triggering an immune system response. Workers' suicidal defenses are also noted in the Brazilian ant *Forelius pusillus*, where a small group of ants leave the safety of the nest each evening after sealing the entrance from the outside.

When threatened by a ladybug, pea aphids can explode themselves, scatter and protect their siblings, and sometimes even kill the ladybug; This form of suicidal altruism is known as autism.[265] Some termite species (for example, *Globitermes sulphureus*) have exploding soldiers that cover their enemies with

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sticks.

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There are anecdotal reports of dogs, horses, and dolphins killing themselves, but few scientific studies of animal suicide. Animal suicide is often reduced to the romantic human interpretation and is not generally considered intentional. Some of the reasons why animals are thought to kill themselves unintentionally include:

1. *psychological stress,*
2. *infection by certain parasites or fungi, or*
3. *ending a longstanding relationship with an owner, and*
4. *hence the breakdown of a longstanding social bond, such as not accepting food from him.*

Among the Youth

Suicide is the leading cause of death among school-age youth. However, suicide is preventable. Teens who are considering suicide often give warning signs of their distress. Parents, teachers, and friends are in a key position to understand these signs and seek help. The most important thing is to never underestimate these warning signs or promise to keep them secret.[46]

Suicide Risk Factors

While far from perfect predictors, certain traits are associated with an increased likelihood of having suicidal thoughts. These include:

Mental illness, including depression, behavioral disorders, and substance abuse.

Family stress/dysfunction.

Environmental risks, including the presence of firearms in the home.

Situational crises (eg, traumatic death of a loved one, physical or sexual abuse, domestic violence).

Suicide Warning Signs

Most suicidal teens display observable behaviors that signal suicidal thoughts. These include:

1. *Suicide threats in the form of direct ("I'm going to kill myself") and indirect ("I wish I didn't wake up again") statements.*
2. *Suicide notes and plans (including online postings).*
3. *Prior suicidal behavior.*
4. *Making final arrangements (for example, making funeral arrangements, writing a will, giving away valuables).*
5. *Don't be preoccupied with death.*
6. *Changes in behavior, appearance, thoughts and/or feelings.*

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What should be done?

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Young people who feel suicidal are unlikely to seek help directly; however, parents, school staff and peers can recognize the warning signs and take immediate action to keep young people safe. When a teenager shows signs that hemay be considering suicide, the following precautions should be taken:

No one should agree to keep a teenager's suicidal thoughts a secret and instead tell a proper caring adult such as a parent, teacher, or school psychologist. Parents should seek help from the school or community mental health resources as soon as possible. School staff should take the student to a mental health professional or administrator working at the school.

School's Role in Suicide Prevention

Children and adolescents spend a significant part of their day at school under the supervision of school staff. Effective suicide and violence prevention is integrated with supportive mental health services, engages the entire school community, and is embedded in a positive school climate through student behavior expectations and a caring and trusting student/adult relationship. Therefore, it is particularly important for all school personnel to be aware of and be alert to risk factors and warning signs of suicidal behavior. All school staff should work to create an environment where students feel safe sharing such information. School psychologists and other crisis response team personnel, including the school counselor and school administrator, are trained to intervene when a student is found to be at risk of suicide. They conduct suicide risk assessments, warn/inform parents, advise and refer to community services, and often supply follow-up counseling and support at school.

Parent Notice and Participation

Even if a young person is judged to be at insignificant risk for suicidal behavior, schools may require parents to sign a document form showing that relevant information has been provided. Parental notices should be documented. Additionally, parents are crucial members of the suicide risk assessment as they have critical information to make a proper risk assessment, including mental health history, family dynamics, recent traumatic events, and earlier suicidal behavior. Once a school has informed a parent of their child's risk of suicide and has supplied referral information, it is the parent's responsibility to seek mental health care for their child.

The causes of suicidal behavior are not fully understood; however, this behavior is clearly due to the complex interplay of many factors. Although many risk factors have been found, they often do not explain why people try to end their lives. In this Review, we describe important recent developments in the theoretical, clinical, and empirical science of psychology about the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors and highlight the crucial importance of psychological factors. Personality and individual differences, cognitive factors, social aspects, and negative life events are important contributors to suicidal behavior. Most people who struggle with suicidal thoughts and behaviors do not seek treatment. Some evidence suggests that different forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy may reduce the risk of suicide attempts, but there is virtually no evidence of factors that protect against suicide. Urgent attention is needed to the development of innovative psychological and psychosocial treatments.

An Important Public Health Cause of Death

Suicide is a major public health problem, causing approximately 800,000 deaths annually worldwide. In the United States, suicide is the 10th leading cause of death with nearly 47,000 total deaths in 2017, and 1.4 million American adults attempted suicide in the same year. While suicide experts and public health officials are understandably preoccupied with suicide deaths and suicide attempts, researchers Jobs and Joiner recently pondered on the large population of people experiencing suicidal ideation, often eluding the attention of our suicide prevention research and clinical treatments. and even national health policies.[47]

The World Health Organization ranks both major depressive disorder (MDD) and bipolar disorder (BD) among the 10 leading causes of disability worldwide. Also, MDD and BD carry a substantial risk of suicide. It is estimated that 25-50% of people diagnosed with BD will try suicide at least once in their lifetime (Goodwin & Jamison, 2007). In addition, bipolar disorder may handle a quarter of all completed suicides (APA, 2013). In depressive disorders, men, and those with a history of suicide attempt/threatened are most at risk for suicide attempts. Individuals with bipolar disorder are approximately 15 times more likely than the general population to try suicide.

For some people with mood disorders, the extreme emotional pain they experience becomes unbearable. Overwhelmed by hopelessness, ravaged by feelings of inadequacy, and burdened by not being able to adequately cope with such feelings, they may view suicide as a reasonable way out. Suicide by CDC "Treat is result of any faith to die, death caused by the behavior of self-harm "is defined as suicide (CDC, 2013), is a result of simultaneously go wrong in many things, in asense. Crosby, Ortega and Melanson, 2011). The person is not only biologically or psychologically vulnerable but must also have the means to commit the act of suicide and lack the necessary protective factors (for example, social support from friends and family, religion, coping skills, and problems). resolution skills that relax the person and enable coping in times of crisis or great psychological pain

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(Berman, 2009).

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Suicide is not listed as a disorder in the DSM-5; however, suffering from a mental disorder – particularly a mood disorder – poses the greatest risk for suicide. Approximately 90% of those who complete suicides have at least one diagnosis of mental disorder, the most common mood disorder (Fleischman, Bertolote, Belfer, & Beautrais, 2005). In fact, the association between major depressive disorder and suicide is so strong that, as discussed in earlier sections, one of the criteria for the disorder is suicidal thoughts (APA, 2013).

Around 1.5% of people worldwide die by suicide. Each year this is about 12 per 100,000 people. Completed suicide rates are generally higher among men than women, ranging from 1.5 times in developing countries to 3.5 times in developed countries. Suicide is usually most common among those over the age of 70; however, in some countries those between the ages of 15 and 30 are at the highest risk. Europe had the highest suicide rates by region in 2015. There are an estimated 10 to 20 million non-fatal suicide tries each year. Non-fatal suicide attempts can lead to injuries and long-term disability. In the western world, suicides are more common among young people and women.

Suicidal thoughts are thoughts of ending one's life, but do not make an active effort for it. Most studies do not distinguish between risk factors for thinking about suicide and risk factors for trying suicide. Risks for suicide attempt rather than mere suicidal ideation include a high pain tolerance and a low fear of death.

Factors that influence suicide risk include mental disorders, drug abuse, psychological conditions, cultural, familial, and social situations, genetics, and experiences of trauma or loss. Mental disorders and substance abuse often coexist. Other risk factors include an earlier suicide attempt, the availability of a means to take someone's life, a family history of suicide, or the presence of a traumatic brain injury. For example, suicide rates were found to be higher in households with firearms than those without weapons.

Socio-economic problems such as unemployment, poverty, homelessness, discrimination can trigger suicidal thoughts. Suicide may be rarer in societies with

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high social cohesion and moral objections to suicide. About 15-40% of PE leave a suicide note. War veterans have a higher risk of suicide, in part because of higher rates of mental illness such as post-traumatic stress disorder and war-related

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physical health issues. Genetics seem to account for 38% to 55% of suicidal behaviors. Suicides can also occur as a local cluster of cases.

The lifetime risk of completed suicide for those hospitalized for suicidal behavior is 8.6%. Comparatively, people who are hospitalized for mood disorders in non-suicidal individuals have a 4% lifetime risk of suicide. Half of all people who die by suicide may have major depressive disorder; Having this or one of the other mood disorders, such as bipolar disorder, increases the risk of suicide by 20 times.

Psychopharmacology for Suicide Risk

Psychiatric care of the mentally ill took a notable turn in the 1950s with the advent of first-generation anti-psychotic drugs. The evolution of psychotropic drugs has been extensive and has begun to shape the prevailing assumptions about suicidal patients – treating a mental disorder is key to reducing the symptoms of suicidal ideation and behavior.

While medications have undoubtedly helped many with mental disorders, there is extensive evidence that targeting and treating mental disorders has little or mixed effect on suicide risk. Despite the widespread use of the drug, limited data (based on randomized controlled trials (RCTs)) on the drug's efficacy on suicidality. For example, immediate use of ketamine for several days on suicidal ideation has short-term effects for some suicidal patients. There is meta-analytical support for lithium carbonate in bipolar patients, and an unrepeatable RCT has shown that clozapine can reduce suicidal ideation and tries in patients with thought disorders. The data on the efficacy of antidepressants at risk for suicide are quite mixed. At present, treatment of mental disorders has had a strong impact on suicidal ideation and behavior. There are three meta-analyses that show little or no effect. Despite the lack of evidence, leading experts insist on the priority of treating mental disorders to reduce the risk of suicide, even with replicates from rigorous randomized controlled trials It downplays the effectiveness of suicidal-focused psychological treatments that have been proven to work based on human data.

Psychosocial Factors

A number of psychological factors increase the risk of suicide: hopelessness, a lack of enjoyment of life, depression, anxiety, agitation, rigid thinking, rumination, thought suppression, and poor coping skills. A poor ability to solve problems, loss of abilities, and poor impulse control also play a role. The feeling of being a burden to others is important in older adults. Those who have never been married are also at greater risk. Recent life stresses, such as the loss of a family member or friend or job loss, may be a contributing factor.

Certain personality factors, particularly prominent levels of neuroticism and introversion, have been associated with suicide. This can make people who are isolated and susceptible to distress more likely to try suicide. On the other hand, optimism has been shown to have a protective effect. Other psychological risk factors include having few reasons to live and feeling trapped in a stressful situation. Changes in the stress response system in the brain can change during suicidal situations.

Prevention

To be balanced and fair, we agree that countless suicidal people are likely to be helped by inpatient psychiatric care and psychotropic medication. However, the lack of suicidal-specific evidence discussed earlier is quite striking. To this end, Jobs argued that some contemporary providers may make assumptions about the putative efficacy of inpatient care and drug use on suicide risk. More importantly, such assumptions can have a major impact on the patient's clinical disposition and even on their entire life. Of particular concern is that some clinicians may find themselves not always working in the patient's best interest because of countertransference issues or fear of being sued if a patient ends their life. Conversely, such problems and fears can lead to overly defensive practices (for example, hospitalizing a patient with passive suicidal thoughts). Furthermore, such practice behaviors may be shaped by a dream that staying in the hospital for three to six days or treating mental disorder with medication is more effective for suicide risk than alternative approaches supported by data.

Therefore, there may be a misconception that a "one-dimensional" approach (that is, a short hospitalization and medication to treat the disorder) will work for all suicidal patients. Another way to understand the possible insistence of some that these approaches are effective is to use Stanford psychologist Carol Dweck's psychological "mentality" concept. Dweck's empirical work has shown the existence of two different mindsets: the "fixed" mindset versus the "growth" mindset. His research shows how these mindsets are reliably linked to different outcomes for personal and professional success, and a growth mindset is linked to much more adaptive and successful outcomes.

Perhaps one of the most important developments in clinical suicidology over the last 20 years has been the development and use of different versions of suicide-focused interventions that focus on stabilization planning for possible acute

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suicidal crises. “In stark contrast to the compelling and unfortunate use of "Harmless Contracts" or "Suicide Contracts", the various stabilization planning interventions for outpatient suicidal patients are more intuitively challenging and

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have proven effective in clinical trial research.[48] The Safety Plan guides the patient through the steps of finding triggers, self-coping techniques, distraction by others, obtaining supportive help, obtaining professional help, and securing deadly paths. Many embraced the Safety Plan Intervention clinically early on as an intuitively better choice for enforcing non-suicide contracts (despite the lack of empirical support for doing so). Relatively recently, however, the superiority of SPI over harmless convention for reducing suicidal attempt behaviors was clearly proved in a large cohort comparison study of suicidal U.S. military veterans and added randomized controlled trial data are currently being conducted.

A conceptual "cousin" of SPI is the "Crisis Response Plan" (CRP), originally developed by Rudd, Joiner, and Rajab, and further elaborated and scrutinized by Bryan and colleagues. In CRP, the patient's note is on an index card, in their own written words, various triggers, coping strategies, resources, and often reasons for living. Bryan and colleagues performed a convincing RCT comparing CRP with innocuous contracts and showed a significant effect on both suicidal ideation and suicide attempts, reducing the latter by 76% at a six-month follow-up evaluation.

Another variation of this theme is the CAMS Stabilization Plan (CSP), developed at the first session of the Collaborative Suicide Assessment and Management (CAMS). Within this therapeutic framework, CSP emphasizes reassurance of lethal methods, followed by a list of coping strategies, resources for access, ways to reduce isolation, and potential barriers to participation in CAMS-guided clinical care. CSP has not been independently studied other than for use within CAMS, but it is a crucial tool routinely used in evidence-based suicidality clinical therapy.

Social isolation and lack of social support have been associated with an increased risk of suicide. Suicide prevention is a term used for collective efforts to reduce the incidence of suicide through preventive measures. Protective factors for suicide include access to support and therapy. About 60% of people with suicidal thoughts do not seek help. Reasons for not doing this include low perceived need and willingness to deal with the problem alone. Despite these high rates, there are effective treatments that focus directly on suicidal thoughts and behaviors and have been proven to reduce suicide attempts in people who need this help.

Dialectical Behavioral Therapy (DBT), Cognitive therapy for suicide prevention

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(CT-SP), and Brief Cognitive behavioral therapy BCBT focus on practicing, paying attention to, and changing suicidal and suicidal behavior thoughts.

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There has been little guidance on how best to meet clinical expectations for the effective care of suicidal patients. In the United States, the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA) sponsored a working group to develop cost-effective and evidence-based approaches to working with suicide risk in outpatient, inpatient, and emergency room settings. The document “Recommended Standard Care for Persons at Risk of Suicide: Health Services Making Suicide Safe” recommends and highlights key approaches for working with suicidal patients.

Cognitive behavioral approaches appear to improve outcomes in young adults who have recently contemplated suicide. School-based programs that increase mental health literacy and train staff have shown mixed results in suicide rates. Economic development can reduce suicide rates through its ability to reduce poverty. Efforts to increase social connection can be effective, especially in older men. Repeated follow-ups can be prevented in people who try suicide. Although crisis helplines are common, there is little evidence to support or refute their effectiveness. Preventing childhood trauma supplies an opportunity to prevent suicide. World Suicide Prevention Day is celebrated on September 10 each year with the support of the International Suicide Prevention Association and the World Health Organization.

Effective Clinical Treatments for Suicide Risk

As discussed, there are more than 80 randomized controlled treatment trials (RCTs) in which suicidal outcomes are the primary focus. In clinical science, RCTs are the gold standard of what has proven to be causally effective because of their reliance on experimental designs and a-priori hypothesis testing. When we consider experimentally validated interventions, RCTs that replicate results top the list, especially when results are replicated by independent researchers. There are a number of promising interventions in a single RCT, for example, the Brief Suicide Attempt Program (ASSIP) and Mentalization-Based Therapy. However, we will focus on treatments with repeated and independent RCT support. These include four different treatments/interventions that have been shown to effectively target suicide.

Dialectical Behavior Therapy

Dialectical Behavioral Therapy (DBT) is the most notable and most researched treatment that has been shown to reduce suicidal behaviors regardless of intent to die.[49] The main purpose of DBT is to teach the patient the skills to regulate emotions and improve relationships with others (suicide is always targeted at the forefront of care). Skills are taught through validation and acceptance with a real focus on behavior change. DBT was one of the first evidence-based treatments shown to be effective in reducing repetitive self-harming behaviors and suicide attempts. More recent results have shown that DBT continues to have an impact on reducing suicidal behaviors among high-risk individuals such as those with borderline personality disorder and on reducing suicidal ideation and self-harm among adolescents. However, while DBT has shown impressive results in managing suicidal behaviors, it is not intended solely to treat suicidality, and repeated results are not consistent across all DBT RCTs to reliably reduce suicidal ideation.

Cognitive Therapy to Prevent Suicide

Another effective therapy targeting the "suicide mode" is Cognitive Therapy for Suicide Prevention (CT-SP). CT-SP treats the clinical features of suicidal behaviors using a variety of cognitive therapy techniques that have proven successful in treating a wide variety of psychiatric disorders. Brown and colleagues found that in a well-powered RCT (an intentionally longer follow-up period of 18 months than in earlier RCTs), patients on CT-SP therapy were 50% less likely to try suicide compared with usual maintenance therapy. The researchers also found significant reductions in depression and hopelessness levels in the CT-SP treatment group compared to the control group. This study showed high internal validity; Replicating the data in a real-world setting (e.g., a community-based outpatient setting) with various samples (e.g., those who have not tried suicide but are having serious thoughts) is the next pending step for CT-SP researchers.

Brief Cognitive Behavioral Therapy

Brief Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (BCBT) has been used in a strong RCT with suicidal, active-duty US Army Soldiers and has been shown to be effective in reducing suicide attempts. As the name suggests, this modality is short (i.e., 12 sessions) to accommodate short-term treatment environments. This variation of CBT suicide-focused care emphasizes co-effective treatment elements, development skills (eg, emotion regulation, mindfulness), focus on suicide mode, and development of self-management. Rudd and colleagues followed up with the soldiers for 24 months and found that compared to the usual treatment, those in the short CBT group were 60% less likely to try suicide.

Collaborative Evaluation and Management of Suicide

Jobes defines Collaborative Assessment and Management of Suicide (CAMS) as a distinctive therapeutic framework targeting suicide. CAMS intervention as a framework, not a new psychotherapy, does not require clinicians to abandon their theoretical orientation or abandon reliable techniques. Indeed, CAMS is within the framework that potentially any treatment could be used. It is a non-denominational approach. When we compare RCTs CAMS with usual care control conditions, there is compelling evidence that CAMS significantly reduces suicidal ideation and general psychiatric distress; it also increases hope and permanence for care. In the RCT comparing DBT to CAMS, CAMS was as successful as DBT in reducing suicide attempts and self-harming behaviors. Beyond the first four published RCTs, five added CAMS RCTs are at various stages of completion and will add to the growing literature.

Little is known about social or environmental associations with human suicidal behavior. Therefore, the purpose of this review was to explore and review the psychosocial correlates suggested to mediate suicidal behaviors. A literature review was conducted on suicide and its risk, risk factors, population characteristics and prediction. Subsequently, articles addressing familial, social, and environmental characteristics as risk factors for suicidal behavior are summarized in a narratively written review. Risk factors for suicide arising from the interaction between the individual and the family context (abuse, loss, family maladjustment) and the interaction between the individual and his or her broader environmental context (stressful life events, social influence, and support) are presented. This overview supplies a summary of recognized psychosocial risk factors for suicidal behavior. Psychosocial characteristics have appeared as a necessary part of suicide risk assessment. Familial, social, and environmental factors, along with psychiatric disorder and biological vulnerability, must be understood in a comprehensive context.

Increasing Rate of Suicide and Suicide Attempts

The increasing rate of suicide and suicide attempts is a growing health problem worldwide. In 2003, the proportion of people who completed suicide in Korea was 25.2 per 100,000.¹ The suicide death rate reported in 2003 was 137% higher than reported 10 years ago, and suicide was the second leading cause of death, particularly among youth aged 15 to 15 years. The suicide attempt rate was also quite high: 1.01% for women and 0.82.2% for men, which is an alarmingly high prevalence rate. Therefore, it is particularly important for mental health professionals to understand the risk factors for suicide and/or suicide attempt. Suicidal behavior occurs in response to interactions between biological, psychological, and socio-environmental risk factors and the relative absence of protective factors.

Suicide and psychosocial factors the 16 factors for suicide, e.g., those including psychological autopsies, focused on the assessment of pathological mental state or psychiatric disorders as potential risk factors. Information on the social and environmental links of suicide and/or suicide attempt is relatively scarce. There is ongoing debate about the relative importance of socio-environmental risk factors compared to psychiatric diagnostic factors in explaining suicidal behavior.⁵ However, among the considerable number of people who show suicidal behavior those at greater risk of trying suicide, the most important aspect of such an assessment is mood. health professionals need to understand every possible risk factor. Therefore, the main purpose of this study was to investigate psychosocial risk factors for suicide and/or suicide attempt by reviewing published research on social, environmental, and familial factors associated with human suicidal behavior.

First, a search was done in Systemic Reviews using suicide as a search term. As a result, 408 review articles were searched. In addition, a narrow and specific search in the Clinical Trial Category that limits the language to English and article type to Review, Meta-analysis, or Randomized Controlled Trial; again, the search term

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was suicide. As a result, 141 articles were found. Sexual abuse attracted the most attention. The relationship between child sexual abuse and suicide has been clearly proved. A cross-sectional study in the Netherlands reported that suicide

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attempts were five times more common in girls and 20 times more common in boys compared to previously sexually abused adolescents. Also, unambiguous evidence was provided in a recent meta-analysis confirming the link between child sexual abuse and suicide as a later adverse effect. They reported that sexual abuse in children had a significant effect on suicide (Glass effect size $d = .44$). Child sexual abuse has been associated with suicide regardless of the victim's age, gender, or socioeconomic status, suggesting that sexual abuse serves as a life event that independently influences suicidal behavior. Lee SI & Jung HY 17 Domestic violence, abuse, and neglect have been associated with suicidal behavior, particularly in children and adolescents. A prospective registry-based study of Danish children found that professionally assessed adolescents hospitalized for abuse or neglect were at increased risk of suicide attempts. It is not yet clear whether the high prevalence of suicidal tendencies is more specifically related to a history of abuse or to a specific outcome of distinct types of psychopathologies or substance abuse following child abuse. In the case of child sexual abuse, a multifaceted traumatization model is supported rather than a specific sexual abuse syndrome that leads to suicidal behavior. According to this view, the impact of sexual abuse is complex because it produces multiple effects on various outcomes such as suicide, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder.

In particular, the loss of a significant other would put survivors in a high-risk situation for suicide. Bereavement studies have confirmed that the mortality rate increases in surviving spouses. People with overt dependency needs will be particularly frustrated after a loss because their security needs are simultaneously blocked. Necessarily, loss of a parent due to separation, divorce, illness, or death in children or adolescents will serve as a strong risk factor for suicide. In a study investigating parental loss as a risk factor for suicide, suicidal patients experienced significantly more maternal loss than non-suicidal patients. In addition, it was revealed that the age at which the patient lost his parents, lost his parents. It is significantly lower in the suicidal group than in the non-suicidal group. A separation reminiscent of a similar event in childhood also means an increased risk of suicide. It is argued that, in addition to the actual loss of another significant other, threatened disappearances, loss of health, or even the loss of a national or cultural affiliation are associated with an increased risk of suicidal behavior. Family factors Empirical research shows that early and chronic life event stressors are

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associated with suicidal behavior, particularly in the family context. Various problems in relationships with close family members often precede suicide. A controlled study has shown that low levels of communication

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between parents and children can act as an important risk factor.⁴ In this study, other factors such as family dissonance, lack of family warmth and impaired parent-child relationships were associated with the child and adolescent. psychopathology, however, did not play a particularly significant role in suicide.

A group of psychopathologies, including parent and sibling substance abuse, violence, and antisocial personality disorder, are associated with suicide or suicide attempts. It is unclear whether these family histories show a genetic predisposition, environmental stressors, or a combination of the two. More interestingly, a family history of suicide and psychosocial factors were found to increase the risk of suicide. Family, twin, and adoption studies consistently revealed that suicidal behavior accumulates in families. Especially maternal suicide attempts were recommended. It is thought to be one of the strongest predictors of adolescents' suicide attempts, along with other factors such as fathers' substance use and family disharmony. Whether genetic factors play a role in the familial transmission of suicide, or the observed familial clustering is caused by the effect of shared environmental factors. Moreover, when the effect of parental psychopathology was statistically controlled, family history of suicidal behavior stayed an important risk factor, suggesting that the effect of family history of suicide is independent of familial clustering.

Stressful Life

Stressful life events often precede suicide or attempted suicide. The occurrence of recent life events was exceedingly high, affecting up to 80% of those who committed suicide. Losing home, not studying, unemployment, financial difficulties, and bankruptcy are common negative life events among people who commit suicide. The significance of these negative life events lies in their actions as a catalyst in the suicidal process. Similarly, the relationship between stressful life events and suicidal behavior in children has been reported. A follow-up study of suicidal attempts in prepubertal inpatients with suicidal ideation showed that highly stressful life events serve as an important risk factor for later suicide attempts. The authors suggested that life-event stressors in the preschool years increase risk for the future. It has been suggested that the stresses of early and chronic life events that lead to family instability, such as relocation, death, loss of relatives, and illness of important caregivers, increase the likelihood of suicidal behavior among children. In addition, legal and disciplinary problems have been found to be associated with an increased risk of suicide, even after adjustment for psychiatric disorders. Environmental impact Suicide can be accelerated by exposure to real or fictional accounts of suicide, such as coming across news about someone else's suicide.

Vulnerable young people are particularly at risk, and the risk is reported to last for about two weeks after exposure.

Facilitating Factors

Disruption in social cohesion before the suicide attempt is started is one of the strongest risk factors for the re-emergence of suicidal behaviors. Children and adolescents with suicidal behavior in social cohesion have been proposed various indicators of poor: dysfunctional relationships between children or adolescents and their family members, poor social skills, leisure skills are weak, vb.17 "Factors that contribute to ' hopelessness ', such as a negative view of one's own efficacy, poor self-esteem, and a sense of responsibility for negative events have been repeatedly found to be associated with suicidality.

Inappropriate coping styles such as impulsivity or catastrophizing will also lead to suicidal behavior.

Social Integration

Suicide micro-SI & Lee Jung HY After reviewing Durkheim beyond the 19 level, which is very weak bond between the individual and society "suggested that " anomie " is a key factor in influencing suicide. Living in a poor area or single-person household is often associated with a high suicide rate. This phenomenon serves as a good example of social fragmentation as a strong predictor of suicide. A national registry-based study of adult suicides in Korea found that lower social class poses a substantial risk for suicide even after controlling for variables such as: such as age, marital status, and place of residence. Family discord or low level of communication and domestic violence are other important risk factors. In addition, family history of suicide, together with parental psychopathology, has an independent effect on suicide and/or suicide attempt. Therefore, these familial, social, and environmental factors implying an important act leading to suicidal behavior should be routinely questioned in the evaluation of those who try suicide.

Solution and Suggestions

It is another controversial issue whether psychosocial risk factors have an independent effect on suicide and/or suicide attempt. Various social and environmental factors were investigated along with familial factors or psychiatric illnesses. For example, in an extensive study by the Canterbury Suicide Project in New Zealand, the authors reported the following common conditions for people who died by suicide: underlying psychological distress or mental illness; discernible mental health or adjustment difficulties prior to the suicide attempt; severe stress or life crisis, often centered on the breakdown of an emotional or supportive relationship; a disturbed or unhappy family and childhood history; socially and educationally disadvantaged background. Recently, in a case-controlled psychological autopsy of 150 suicide victims, it has been suggested that suicide is mediated: unemployment, indebtedness, celibacy, lack of social support, psychiatric illness, and history of intervention.³⁸ The authors noted that suicide risk was independently mediated by both psychosocial and clinical factors. The effect size of psychosocial factors has been suggested to be comparable to previously reported psychiatric disorders.^{4,39} However, there is no single risk factor or any risk factor. The combination of the above items is acceptable to decide future suicidal behavior in suicidal attempters to a precise or useful degree. ⁴⁰, various risk factors may combine to lead to suicidal behavior. For example, acute mood swings that lead to suicidal ideation when a person with an active disorder (eg, mood or substance use disorder) experiences a stressful event, usually caused by an underlying condition (loss, humiliation, trouble with the law or school, etc.) (anxiety, hopelessness, anger) occur. At this point, an underlying trait (for example, impulsivity) or a lack of social support may ease suicidal ideation leading to a true suicidal act.⁶ In conclusion, it is important to understand individual risk factors for suicide from an integrative perspective. Clinicians need to consider not only interactions between the individual and family at the micro level, but also interactions between the individual and the broader environmental context.

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Psychosocial risk factors, such as acute or chronic stressors, suicidal facilitators,
and background factors

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involved in suicide, should be considered in a comprehensive context, along with the individual's mental or pathological states and biological vulnerability.

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Suicide prevention strategies revisited: 10-year systematic review. *Lancet Psychiatry* (2016) 3(7):646–59. doi: 10.1016/S2215-0366(16)30030-X
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[8] SSAs are epidemiologically terribly like those who die by suicide and may therefore serve to study suicides. The authors concluded that the interaction of mental pain, interpersonal factors, and impaired decision making are crucial for suicide risk assessment and research.

[9] They suggest that, in addition to anxiety and depressive symptoms, cognitive deficits in psychiatric patients include important therapeutic targets.

[10] They found that it was significantly associated with a marked increase in suicidal behaviors and thoughts.

[11] Secure attachment to one's father moderated the relationship between sibling bullying and depression/suicidal ideation.

[12] The study found a relatively low threshold for triggering involuntary attentional changes in suicidal patients; this is a factor that may play a role in reported distractions.

[13] TRQ-SF correlated positively with patient suicide outcomes, depression severity, and concurrent and predictive assessments of clinicians' judgments about patient suicide risk. However, TRQ-SF did not predict global symptom severity, thus specifically showing suicidal responses.

[14] Some evidence suggests that different forms of cognitive and behavioral therapy may reduce the risk of suicide attempts, but there is almost no evidence on factors that protect against suicide. Urgent attention is needed to the development of innovative psychological and psychosocial treatments.

[15] Although his area of expertise has grown considerably over the past few decades, most psychological scientific research to date has focused on suicidal ideation and suicide tries rather than deaths by suicide.

[16] University of Glasgow, Glasgow, United Kingdom (Prof RC O'Connor PhD); and Psychology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA, USA (Prof MK Nock PhD) Correspondence: Prof Rory C O'Connor, Suicidal Behavior Research Laboratory, University of Glasgow, Academic Center, Gartnavel Royal Hospital, Glasgow, G12 0XH

[17] Diabetes-stress models postulate that the negative consequences of pre-existing frailty factors are particularly pronounced when activated by stress. Schotte and Clum¹⁰ and Mann and colleagues¹² supported the diathesis-stress perspective.

[18] When talent is high, desire is likely to translate into suicidal behavior. The schematic assessment model of suicide is described by Johnson et al. (2008).

[19] Acquired ability includes reduced fear of death and increased tolerance for physical pain.

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[20] While belonging and burden are crucial in the final common path to suicide in interpersonal theory, feelings of defeat (i.e., feeling defeated after triggering circumstances) and being trapped (i.e., inability to escape from fear)

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[21] Each of these factors, independently or in combination with other factors, may contribute to the risk of suicide. Some of the factors are associated with the occurrence of suicidal ideation, while others increase the likelihood of suicidal thoughts acting.

[22] Suicidal ability Fatal (or nearly lethal) suicide tries Interpersonal suicide theory Courtesy of the American Psychological Association from Van Orden et al.

[23] In particular, perfectionistic beliefs may interact with other factors (eg, negative life events, difficulties, and cognitions) to prevent recovery from a suicidal event or to further increase the risk of suicidal ideation and self-harm.

[24] eg, integrated motivational-volitional model of suicidal behavior, courtesy of John Wiley & Sons from O'Connor⁸

[25] There is little evidence of a protective effect. The context of suicide risk...

[26] Rumination, which refers to repetitive focusing on one's own distress symptoms, has been associated with suicidal thoughts and attempts. Rumination, which refers to a repetitive focus on one's own distress symptoms, has been associated with suicidal thoughts and attempts.

[27] Reflections and attempts, rumination, are more strongly associated with suicide

[28] See the Series Article by Pitman et al. page 86

[29] Risk of later suicidal behavior.

[30] Research efforts to distinguish between suicidal thoughts, suicidal attempts, and recurrent attempts should be given priority, as understanding the factors that enable or inhibit behavioral resuscitation will inform the development of intervention studies.

[31] More than 800,000 deaths a year (WHO, 2014), most of them young people aged 15-29 years (Nock et al., 2013; WHO, 2012); a situation with serious economic consequences for our world today (Kinyanda, Hoskins, Nakku, Nawaz, & Patel, 2012). For this reason, the World Health Organization's 2008 Gap Action Program included suicide as one of the priorities for serious attention and action.

[32] Despite some progress, research evidence on suicide in Ghana so far has mostly focused on adult suicide (Adinkrah, 2012; Akotia, Knizek, Kinyanda, & Hjelmeland, 2014; Asare-Doku, Osafo, & Akotia, 2017; Osafo et al. ., 2016; Osafo, Akotia, Andoh-Arthur, & Quarshie, 2015; Sefa-Dedeh & Canetto, 1992) and younger populations such as university students and less studies on other vulnerable groups such as children, youth, and the elderly (Eshun, 1999, 2003; Nanewortor, 2011) is an example.

[33] Participating in suicide calls is one of the critical events that ambulance personnel have identified as causing an emotional burden and therefore contributing to their mental health and well-being.

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[34] This scoping review aims to describe the current state of research in this area. Specific questions guiding this literature review are: What is known about the prevalence of suicide exposure among mental health professionals and first responders? What are the personal and

professional effects of exposure to suicide on mental health professionals and first responders? and what are the gaps in the literature on suicide exposure among first responders and mental health professionals?

[35] No article discussing suicide among mental health professionals that PTSD and burnout are the only mental health outcomes investigated.

[36] Personal and professional life, how it is experienced and managed, links to suicide risks in these groups, and how this and other emotional distress can be reduced.

[37] Looking back, one wonders whether the scholarship is a trail of breadcrumbs captivating lifelong to solve the puzzle of depressed self, an unconscious attempt.

[38] Measures against suicide (social support, self-esteem, and life purpose).

[39] Some suicides are impulsive acts due to stress (such as financial or academic difficulties), relationship problems (such as separation), or harassment/bullying. Those who have tried suicide before are at higher risk for future attempts. Effective suicide prevention efforts include limiting access to suicide methods such as firearms, drugs, and poisons; treatment of mental disorders and substance abuse; careful media coverage of suicide; and improving economic conditions. Although crisis helplines are common, they are not well-studied.

[40] Most studies do not distinguish between risk factors that lead to thinking about suicide and risk factors that lead to suicide attempts. Risks for suicide attempt rather than mere suicidal ideation include a high pain tolerance and a low fear of death.

[41] Others estimate that about half of people who complete suicide will be diagnosed with a personality disorder, with borderline personality disorder the most common. About 5% of schizophrenic patients die by suicide. Eating disorders are another high-risk condition.

[42] Specifically, changes in the polyamine system and hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis.

[43] sleep disorders such as insomnia and sleep apnea are risk factors for depression and suicide. In some cases, sleep disturbances may be a risk factor independent of depression.

[44] There seems to be a link between air pollution and depression and suicide.

[45] Arguments about the moral or social acceptability of suicide range from the position that the act is inherently immoral and unacceptable under any circumstances, to the view that suicide is a sacred right of all who rationally and conscientiously believe that they have committed suicide. to the decision to end their own lives, even if they are young and healthy.

[46] When all adults and students in the school community are committed to making suicide prevention a priority and are empowered to take the right actions, we can help young people before they engage in irreversible behavior.

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[47] 10,600,000 American adults in the United States experience severe suicidal thoughts – an alarming cohort that dwarfs the population of those who try and commit suicide.

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[48] The best known of these interventions is the Safety Plan Intervention (SPI), developed by Drs. Stanley and Brown. Widely adopted in American Veterans Affairs and US Department of Defense healthcare systems, SPI has been adopted in the public and private sectors as an alternative to coercive contracts that focus on what a patient has promised not to do (i.e., kill himself). suicidal, versus planning what to do in a dark crisis.

[49] DBT has four main components: individual therapy, skills training, telephone coaching, and a counseling team.